

Supplementary Material

Details of the Multivocal Review (Databases, Snowballing, and Grey Literature)

This appendix provides the supplementary material for the multivocal review conducted in this study, focusing on *transparency*, *traceability*, and *verifiability*. The content includes the description of the *snowballing* protocol, the identification and justification of the seed papers, the consolidated results (including an adapted PRISMA), as well as the scope and findings of the *grey literature* review. This data complements the main article’s methodological sections (see, for example,

The procedure adopted in this research followed two main steps: (i) the definition of an initial set of seed papers and (ii) successive iterations of references and citations. The initial step began with a structured search in the IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, and ScienceDirect databases, chosen for their relevance in the field of Software Engineering and Artificial Intelligence.

From this initial set of articles, the *snowballing* iterations were conducted, exploring references (*backward*) and citations (*forward*), until theoretical saturation was reached—that is, the point at which new rounds no longer added studies relevant to the research question. This systematic approach ensures methodological traceability and transparency.

The initial step consisted of selecting seed papers through a structured search. The search string was constructed to combine the domains of Artificial Intelligence and retrospectives in the context of Scrum:

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("Artificial Intelligence" OR "Machine Learning")  
AND ("Scrum")  
AND ("Retrospective" OR "Sprint Retrospective")
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The queries were run in the IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, and ScienceDirect databases, widely recognized in the areas of Software Engineering and Information Systems. Filters were applied for language (English), publication period (2019–2025), publication type (conference and peer-reviewed journal articles), and subject area (Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Information Systems). For the definition of the initial set of seed papers, which served as the starting point for executing the *snowballing*, the following inclusion criteria were applied:

- **Publication Period:** Studies published between 2019 and 2025, covering recent advances in applied AI in agile contexts;
- **Publication Type:** Articles from peer-reviewed conferences or journals (IEEE, ACM, Elsevier, Springer, among others);
- **Subject Area:** Research linked to the areas of Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Information Systems, or agile practices;
- **Scope:** Works that address at least one of the following aspects:
 1. Application of AI or analytics in agile practices;
 2. Use of AI/analytics to support decision-making in agile teams;
 3. Discussion of Scrum retrospectives or related continuous improvement ceremonies.
- **Language:** Publications in English.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies published before 2019;
- Non-peer-reviewed works (academically unvalidated grey literature);
- Purely technical AI articles unrelated to agile practices;
- Agile/Scrum studies with no connection to AI, analytics, or decision support;
- Duplicates across different indexing databases;
- Research whose primary focus belongs to other domains (e.g., health, manufacturing, education) with no direct relation to the agile context.

Table 1: Seed papers selected for the *snowballing* process

ID	Reference	Justification
S1	Dam, H. K.; Tran, T.; Grundy, J.; Ghose, A.; Kamei, Y. (2019). <i>Towards effective AI-powered agile project management</i>	Pioneer in discussing the application of AI in agile management, establishing conceptual foundations for the use of AI in software processes.
S2	Sandoval-Alfaro, O. E.; Quintero-Meza, R. R. (2021). <i>Application of data analytics techniques for decision making in the retrospective stage of the Agile Scrum methodology</i>	Directly applies analytics techniques in Scrum retrospectives, aligning with the central research question.
S3	Mdallal, R.; et al. (2023). <i>AI-powered conceptual model for Scrum framework</i>	Proposes a conceptual model integrating AI into the Scrum framework, serving as a reference for integration into agile ceremonies.

Table 2: Summary of the seed paper selection process (adapted PRISMA)

Stage / Database	IEEE Xplore	ACM DL	ScienceDirect	Total
Initial results	2	100	88	190
After duplicate removal	2	95	85	182
After automated filters	2	45	32	79
Screened by title/abstract	2	45	32	79
Included as seed	1	1	1	3

Executing the process from the three seed papers resulted in two main iterations. In the first, 63 articles were analyzed, and 11 relevant studies were included in the final corpus. In the second, 1,072 articles were identified from references and citations, of which 146 were included after applying the selection criteria. Summing the two rounds, the resulting final corpus consists of 157 articles, which form the evidence base for qualitative analysis and methodological triangulation in this research.

Table 3: Summary of the snowballing process (two iterations)

Seed	Identified (Iter. 1)	Included (Iter. 1)	Identified (Iter. 2)	Included (Iter. 2)
S1	25	2	425	15
S2	24	3	148	38
S3	14	6	499	93
Total	63	11	1,072	146

Figure 1: Adapted PRISMA flowchart for seed paper selection.

Table 4 presents the articles included after all *snowballing* iterations, with their respective IDs, references, and inclusion justifications. This set constitutes the triangulated evidence base in this dissertation.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S1-B2	Auth, G., Jöhnk, J., & Wiecha, D. A. (2021). <i>A Conceptual Framework for Applying Artificial Intelligence in Project Management</i> . IEEE CBI.	Interviews in German companies; proposes a conceptual framework for adopting AI in project management. Broadens the discussion on practical adoption in Agile/Scrum.
S1-B3	Biesialska, K., Franch, X., & Muntés-Mulero, V. (2021). <i>Big Data analytics in Agile software development: A systematic mapping study</i> . Information and Software Technology, 132, 106448.	Mapping of 88 studies on analytics in Agile. Provides a comprehensive overview and connects trends to your RQ.
S2-B1	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Ghose, A., & Grundy, J. (2018). <i>Predicting Delivery Capability in Iterative Software Development</i> . IEEE TSE.	ML models to predict delivery capability in iterative cycles. Supports predictive decision-making in agile contexts.
S2-B2	Arora, M., Verma, S., Kavita, & Chopra, S. (2020). <i>Systematic Literature Review of Machine Learning Estimation Approaches in Scrum Projects</i> . In Cognitive Informatics and Soft Computing. Springer.	Systematic review of ML applied to estimation in Scrum. Directly connects with effort prediction in agile teams.
S2-B3	Matthies, C. (2019). <i>Agile Process Improvement in Retrospectives</i> . ICSE Companion.	Explores retrospectives as a mechanism for continuous improvement. Highly relevant to your RQ on retrospectives.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B1	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Pham, T. T. M., Ghose, A., & Menzies, T. (2018). <i>A deep learning model for estimating story points</i> . IEEE TSE.	LSTM neural networks applied to story point estimation in Scrum. Relevant to automating planning practices.
S3-B2	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Ghose, A., & Grundy, J. (2017). <i>Predicting the delay of issues with due dates in software projects</i> . Empirical Software Engineering, 22(3), 1223–1263.	Predicting issue delays using ML. Connects with risk management in agile projects.
S3-F1	Hoda, R., Dam, H. K., Tantithamthavorn, C., Thongtanunam, P., & Storey, M. A. (2023). <i>Augmented Agile: Human-Centered AI-Assisted Software Management</i> . IEEE Software.	Proposes “Augmented Agile,” where AI assists but does not replace human judgment. Central to human–AI trust in retrospectives.
S3-F2	Shahriary, A., Sedighi, M., Tajik, N., Shahinfar, M., & Asiyabar, A. R. (2025). <i>Assessing Large Language Models as Agile Scrum Masters: A Comparative Study of Project Planning Efficiency</i> . ICWR 2025.	Comparative study of LLMs acting as artificial Scrum Masters. Links LLMs to leadership roles in Scrum.
S3-F3	Kula, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2024). <i>Context-Aware Automated Sprint Plan Generation for Agile Software Development</i> . ASE 2024.	Proposal for automatic sprint plan generation with AI support. Direct support for decision-making in agile planning.
S3-F4	Taboada, I., Daneshpajouh, A., Toledo, N., & de Vass, T. (2023). <i>Artificial Intelligence Enabled Project Management: A Systematic Literature Review</i> . Applied Sciences, 13(8), 5014.	Systematic review on the role of AI in project management. Highlights trends and barriers.
S1-B2-B1	Dutta, A., Bose, I., & Kumar, M. (2020). <i>Adoption of artificial intelligence in project management</i> . International Journal of Project Management.	Empirical study of factors influencing AI adoption in PM, based on a survey with managers. Identifies organizational, cultural, and technical barriers. Aligned with the RQ by highlighting practical obstacles to adopting AI in PM practices. Notes: Connects with barrier categories seen in S3.
S1-B2-B2	Marnewick, C. (2020). <i>The reality of artificial intelligence in project management</i> . International Journal of Managing Projects in Business.	Analyzes maturity and expectations regarding AI in PM in South African companies. Practical evidence that AI in PM is still in early adoption; useful for triangulation.
S1-B2-B3	Jöhnk, J., et al. (2021). <i>Enablers and inhibitors for artificial intelligence adoption: an empirical study in the German energy sector</i> . Information Systems Frontiers.	Explores critical factors for AI adoption in regulated sectors. Reinforces evidence about organizational and technical barriers.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S1-B2-B4	Misirlis, N., & Vlachopoulou, M. (2018). <i>Social media metrics and analytics in project management</i> . Procedia Computer Science.	Analyzes the use of social metrics and big data in PM. Points to gaps in using analytics for insights—relevant to retrospectives.
S1-B2-B5	Serrador, P., & Pinto, J. K. (2015). <i>Does Agile work? — A quantitative analysis of agile project success</i> . International Journal of Project Management.	Global survey-based quantitative study on factors of success in agile projects. Bridges Agile + project success, serving as quantitative grounding for AI to support retros and metrics.
S1-B2-F1	Salimimoghadam, S., Ghanbaripour, A. N., Tumpa, R. J., Rahimi, A. K., Golmoradi, M., Rashidian, S., & Skitmore, M. (2025). <i>The Rise of Artificial Intelligence in Project Management: A Systematic Literature Review of Current Opportunities, Enablers, and Barriers</i> . Buildings, 15(7), 1130.	Systematic review identifying opportunities, barriers, and enablers for AI in PM. Provides broad state-of-the-art basis, useful to triangulate barriers and opportunities.
S1-B2-F2	Craveiro, M. G., & Domingues, L. (2025). <i>Artificial Intelligence on Project Management Performance Domains</i> . Procedia Computer Science, 256, 1583.	Analyzes how AI can be applied to the PMI performance domains. Expands methodological discussion by connecting AI to recognized PM frameworks.
S1-B2-F3	Barakat, O., & El Farissi, N. (2025). <i>Catalysts Driving the Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Project Management: An In-Depth Exploration with a Focus on the Moroccan Context</i> . Digital Economy. Emerging Technologies and Business Innovation, 530, 366.	Empirical study in Morocco identifying motivators and barriers for integrating AI in PM. Practical evidence in an emerging context; relevant for international comparison.
S1-B3-F1	Taboada, I., Daneshpajouh, A., Toledo, N., & De Vass, T. (2023). <i>Artificial intelligence enabled project management: a systematic literature review</i> . Applied Sciences.	Systematic review synthesizing literature on AI in PM within Industry 5.0. Updated state of the art, relevant for triangulating with S1-B2 and S3.
S1-B3-F2	Jamarani, A., Haddadi, S., & Sarvizadeh, R. (2024). <i>Big data and predictive analytics: A systematic review of applications</i> . Artificial Intelligence Review.	Maps predictive big data applications, covering software and project management. Provides a broad view of predictive analytics applicable to Agile.
S1-B3-F3	Barata, S. F. P. G., & Ferreira, F. A. F. (2023). <i>Determinants of E-commerce, artificial intelligence, and agile methods in small-and medium-sized enterprises</i> . IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management.	Analyzes determinants of joint adoption of Agile and AI in SMEs. Practical evidence in resource-constrained environments; useful for triangulation.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S1-B3-F4	Bai, S., Shi, S., Han, C., Yang, M., & Gupta, B. B. (2024). <i>Prioritizing user requirements for digital products using explainable artificial intelligence: A data-driven analysis on video conferencing apps</i> . Future Generation Computer Systems.	Uses XAI to prioritize software requirements in agile cycles. Directly connects explainable AI with backlog/refinement.
S1-B3-F5	Shameem, M., Nadeem, M., & Zamani, A. T. (2023). <i>Genetic algorithm based probabilistic model for agile project success in global software development</i> . Applied Soft Computing.	Predictive model using genetic algorithms for success in distributed agile projects. Technical evidence of AI application in distributed agile environments.
S1-B3-F6	Rath, S. P., Jain, N. K., Tomar, G., & Singh, A. K. (2025). <i>A systematic literature review of agile software development projects</i> . Information and Software Technology.	SLR on agile practices covering quality, metrics, and challenges. Methodological update; relevant for crossing with AI metrics.
S1-B3-F7	Wulandari, H., & Raharjo, T. (2023). <i>Systematic Literature and Expert Review of Agile Methodology Usage in Business Intelligence Projects</i> . Journal of Information Systems.	Combines SLR + expert review on BI in Agile. Connects Agile + analytics with insights applicable to AI.
S2-B1-B1	Hassan, A. E. (2008). <i>The road ahead for mining software repositories</i> . 2008 Frontiers of Software Maintenance. IEEE.	Seminal MSR paper arguing for its potential to support decisions in software engineering. Conceptual basis for using historical data (issues, commits) in agile project predictions. Notes: Connects with delivery prediction in iterations; used as methodological foundation.
S2-B1-B2	Nagappan, N., Murphy, B., & Basili, V. (2013). <i>The influence of organizational structure on software quality: an empirical case study</i> . ICSE.	Links organizational structure and software quality at Microsoft. Relevant for exploring factors beyond technical metrics that affect delivery. Notes: Supports discussion of organizational variables in AI predictions.
S2-B1-B3	Herzig, K., Just, S., & Zeller, A. (2013). <i>It's not a bug, it's a feature: How misclassification impacts bug prediction</i> . ICSE.	Analyzes how issue misclassification undermines defect prediction models. Directly related to the risk of using issue data in automated predictions. Notes: Complements S2-B1's methodological critique.
S2-B1-B4	Zimmermann, T., Premraj, R., & Zeller, A. (2007). <i>Predicting defects for Eclipse</i> . PROMISE.	Defect prediction model based on software metrics and project history in Eclipse. A precursor to ML-based failure prediction, aligned with delivery capability prediction. Notes: Shows large-scale applications, connecting with agile practices.
S2-B1-F1	Lorshan, N., Wijerathna, P. M. A. K., & Kumara, B. T. G. S. (2025). <i>Prediction of Sprint Delivery Capability in Agile Software Development Using Machine Learning</i> . SCSE.	Applies ML algorithms to predict sprint delivery capability using performance history and agile metrics. Directly expands work on delivery prediction in agile environments.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S2-B1-F2	Choetkiertikul, M., Banyongrakkul, P., Ragkhitwetsagul, C., Tuarob, S., Dam, H. K., & Sunetnanta, T. (2025). <i>Sprint2Vec: A Deep Characterization of Sprints in Iterative Software Development</i> . IEEE TSE.	Introduces vector representations of sprints for automated pattern analysis and performance prediction. Methodological contribution to predictive analysis in Scrum.
S2-B1-F3	Tawosi, V., Moussa, R., & Sarro, F. (2023). <i>Agile Effort Estimation: Have We Solved the Problem Yet? Insights From a Replication Study</i> . IEEE TSE.	Replication study on effort estimation techniques in agile projects, evaluating accuracy and limitations. Relates to the core challenge of estimation in Scrum—fundamental for decision support.
S2-B1-F4	Yin, M., Meng, D., Zhu, D., Wang, Y., & Jiang, J. (2023). <i>Predicting Changes in User-Driven Requirements Using Conditional Random Fields in Agile Software Development</i> . IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management.	Proposes a CRF model to predict changes in user-driven requirements in agile contexts. Focuses on dynamic requirements management—critical in retrospectives and planning.
S2-B1-F5	Kula, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2021). <i>Modeling Team Dynamics for the Characterization and Prediction of Delays in User Stories</i> . ASE.	Analyzes agile team dynamics and uses predictive models to identify user-story delays. Relevant for forecasting risks in Scrum cycles and supporting facilitator decisions.
S2-B1-F6	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Pham, T., Ghose, A., & Menzies, T. (2019). <i>A Deep Learning Model for Estimating Story Points</i> . IEEE TSE.	Deep learning model to automate story point estimation in agile backlogs. Aligned with applying AI to optimize Scrum estimates.
S2-B2-B1	Wen, J., Li, S., Lin, Z., Hu, Y., & Huang, C. (2012). <i>Systematic literature review of machine learning based software development effort estimation models</i> . Information and Software Technology, 54(1), 41–59.	Systematic review covering ML models for effort estimation in software (not exclusively Agile). Provides state-of-the-art baseline for ML applied to estimation—useful for comparison with Scrum.
S2-B2-B2	Usman, M., Mendes, E., & Börstler, J. (2015). <i>Effort estimation in Agile software development: a survey on the state of the practice</i> . ACM.	Empirical survey with agile teams analyzing real estimation practices in Scrum/Agile. Highlights practical gaps that ML can fill in agile environments.
S2-B2-B3	Dragicevic, S., Celar, S., & Turic, M. (2017). <i>Bayesian network model for task effort estimation in Agile software development</i> . Journal of Systems and Software, 127, 109–119.	Bayesian network model applied to task estimation in Scrum. Applies probabilistic techniques directly in the agile context.
S2-B2-B4	Idri, A., Hosni, M., & Abran, A. (2016). <i>Systematic literature review of ensemble effort estimation</i> . Journal of Systems and Software.	Review of ensemble techniques for effort estimation. Contributes to the discussion on meta-heuristics and combined models, also analyzed in S2-B2.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S2-B2-B5	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H.K., Tran, T., Pham, T.T.M., Ghose, A., & Menzies, T. (2016). <i>A deep learning model for estimating story points</i> . IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering.	Proposes a deep neural network for story point estimation in agile projects. One of the first to apply DL directly to Scrum.
S2-B2-B6	Panda, A., Satapathy, S. M., & Rath, S. K. (2015). <i>Empirical validation of neural network models for Agile software effort estimation based on story points</i> . Procedia Computer Science, 57, 772–781.	Empirical validation of neural networks for estimation in Scrum. Aligned with the RQ on ML in Scrum.
S2-B2-B7	Satapathy, S. M., & Rath, S. K. (2017). <i>Empirical assessment of machine learning models for Agile software development effort estimation using story points</i> . Innovations in Systems and Software Engineering, 13(2-3), 191–200.	Compares ML algorithms for story point-based estimates. Relevant for comparing accuracy across ML methods in Scrum.
S2-B2-B8	Bilgaiyan, S., Sagnika, S., Mishra, S., & Das, M. (2016). <i>A review of software cost estimation in Agile software development using soft computing techniques</i> . 2nd Int. Conf. on Computational Intelligence and Networks (CINE), 112–117.	Review focused on soft computing techniques applied to estimation in Agile. Complements S2-B2 by adding additional evidence.
S2-B2-F1	Alsaadi, B., & Saeedi, K. (2022). <i>Data-driven effort estimation techniques of agile user stories: a systematic literature review</i> . Artificial Intelligence Review.	Systematic review of data-driven techniques for effort estimation of user stories. Highly relevant, providing a comprehensive view of estimation practices in Scrum.
S2-B2-F2	Butt, S. A., Khalid, A., Ercan, T., et al. (2022). <i>A software-based cost estimation technique in Scrum using a developer's expertise</i> . Engineering Software.	Proposes a technique based on developer expertise for cost estimation. Relevant for understanding hybrid estimation approaches in Scrum.
S2-B2-F3	Arora, M., Verma, S., Kavita, et al. (2022). <i>An efficient ANFIS-EEBAT approach to estimate effort of Scrum projects</i> . Scientific Reports.	Uses ANFIS to improve accuracy in Scrum effort estimates. Directly complements the seed paper, deepening practical application.
S2-B2-F4	Alsaadi, B., & Saeedi, K. (2024). <i>Ensemble effort estimation for novice agile teams</i> . Information and Software Technology.	Proposes ensemble methods to improve estimation for novice agile teams. Strong connection with accuracy improvement in Scrum.
S2-B2-F5	Antaputra, A. M. M., & Yong, L. T. (2024). <i>A systematic literature review on Agile Requirements Engineering and Artificial Intelligence</i> . IEEE.	SLR analyzing the integration of AI in requirements engineering for agile environments. Relevant for the intersection of AI, requirements, and Scrum.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S2-B2-F6	Sakhrawi, Z., Sellami, A., & Bouassida, N. (2022). <i>Support vector regression for enhancement effort prediction of Scrum projects</i> . Innovations in Systems and Software Engineering.	Uses SVR to predict enhancement effort in Scrum based on COSMIC. Brings a robust technical approach applied to Scrum.
S2-B2-F7	Hariyanti, E., Paradista, M. A., et al. (2024). <i>The Implementation of Machine Learning for Software Effort Estimation: A Literature Review</i> . Journal of Information Systems.	Review on ML use for software effort estimation. Provides a consolidated view of ML's role in Scrum.
S2-B2-F8	Sakhrawi, Z., Sellami, A., & Bouassida, N. (2022). <i>Software Enhancement Effort Estimation using Stacking Ensemble Model within the Scrum Projects</i> . IC-SOFT.	Proposes an ensemble model for estimation in Scrum. Contributes advanced techniques applied to Scrum contexts.
S2-B2-F9	Singh, D., Sharma, A., Rakhra, M., et al. (2025). <i>Deep learning for agile effort estimation</i> . AIP Conference Proceedings.	Proposes deep neural networks for effort estimation in Agile. Advances techniques applied to the Scrum context.
S2-B2-F10	Pérez-Castillo, Y. J., Orantes-Jiménez, S. D., et al. (2024). <i>A systematic literature review on machine learning applications for agile project management</i> . Ingeniería Investigación y Tecnología.	SLR mapping ML applications in Agile PM. Broad basis to connect AI with Agile.
S2-B2-F11	Baumgartner, A. (2022). <i>Applying soft computing for effort estimation in agile software projects: Literature review</i> . Doria.fi.	Review on soft computing applied to effort estimation. Deepens methodological discussion in the agile context.
S2-B2-F12	Chopra, S., & Malik, A. (2024). <i>A neoteric review of story point estimation in Agile-Scrum projects using machine and deep learning algorithms</i> . Taylor & Francis.	Review of ML/DL techniques for story point estimation in Scrum. Direct alignment with the RQ on AI in Scrum practices.
S2-B2-F13	Pérez-Castillo, Y. J., Orantes-Jiménez, S. D., et al. (2024). <i>Comprehensive analysis of the contributions of machine learning to efficiency in Agile project management</i> . POLIBITS.	Analyzes how ML contributes to efficiency in Agile PM. Clear connection between ML and performance improvement in Agile.
S2-B2-F14	Arora, M., Raj, R., Jaiswal, A., Singh, R., & Nain, A. (2023). <i>An ANFIS-driven estimation of effort in Agile Scrum projects</i> . SSRN Proceedings.	Extension of ANFIS work for effort estimation in Scrum. Complements ANFIS studies in Scrum projects.
S2-B2-F15	Singh, D., Sharma, A., & Malik, A. (2021). <i>Deep learning inspired continuous estimation framework for Scrum projects</i> . OAPEN.	DL-based framework for continuous estimation in Scrum. Strong methodological contribution aligned with the RQ.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S2-B3-B	Santana, C., Queiroz, F., Vasconcelos, A., & Gusmão, C. (2015). <i>Software Process Improvement in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review</i> . Euromicro SEAA.	SLR of 423 papers on agile process improvement, highlighting the need to adapt SPI to agile contexts. Solid conceptual basis linking SPI to Agile; methodological reference. <i>Note:</i> Complements the empirical methods gap in Matthies.
S2-B3-B	Kuhrmann, M., Konopka, C., Nellesmann, P., Diebold, P., & Münch, J. (2015). <i>Software Process Improvement: Where is the Evidence? Initial Findings from a Systematic Mapping Study</i> . ICSSP.	Mapping study on SPI over 25 years, showing increased interest in agile methods. Provides historical context and reinforces the relevance of agile adoption in SPI. <i>Note:</i> Brings complementary empirical evidence.
S2-B3-B	Hoda, R., Noble, J., & Marshall, S. (2010). <i>Organizing Self-Organizing Teams</i> . ICSE.	Explores how self-organizing teams structure processes, proposing emergent practices. Relevant to retrospectives as a space for autonomy and improvement. <i>Note:</i> Connects self-management to evolving practices in retrospectives.
S2-B3-B	Richter, I., Raith, F., & Weber, M. (2016). <i>Problems in Agile Global Software Engineering Projects especially within Traditionally Organised Corporations</i> . C3S2E.	Identifies coordination problems in global agile projects and proposes adaptation insights. Expands the discussion to distributed contexts, relevant for retrospectives. <i>Note:</i> May provide nuance on organizational challenges.
S2-B3-F	Firdaus, M. B., Patulak, I. M., Tejawati, A., Bryantama, A., Putra, G. M., & Pakpahan, H. S. (2019). <i>Agile-Scrum Software Development Monitoring System</i> . 2019 International Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Information Engineering (ICEEIE), 6, 288–293.	Presents a monitoring system for agile development using Scrum, focusing on metrics to track progress. Relevant for exploring how metrics can support retrospectives and continuous monitoring. <i>Note:</i> Connects practical tools to the continuous improvement context in retrospectives.
S2-B3-F	Guerrero-Calvache, M., & Hernández, G. (2024). <i>Métricas para la evaluación de factores de productividad de equipo en desarrollo ágil de software: un mapeo sistemático de literatura</i> . <i>Tecnológicas</i> , 27(59), e2918.	Systematic mapping on productivity metrics in agile teams, emphasizing factors impacting performance. Aligns with the RQ by addressing measurement of productivity and effectiveness in agile teams, a central theme in retrospectives. <i>Note:</i> Complements the literature by providing a broad view of applicable metrics.
S3-B1-B1	Porru, S., Damiani, E., & Marchesi, M. (2016). <i>Estimating story points from issue reports</i> . In Proc. ESEM.	Proposes an initial SP estimation model from issue-report features (e.g., type, component, text). Foundational work for agile story point estimation; used as a baseline for Deep-SE. <i>Notes:</i> Direct connection to automated metrics for retrospectives.
S3-B1-B2	Mao, K., Capra, L., Harman, M., & Jia, Y. (2017). <i>A survey of the use of crowdsourcing in software engineering</i> . <i>Journal of Systems and Software</i> , 126, 57–84.	Overview of crowdsourcing in SE, including data labeling and quality evaluation. Relevant for connecting collaborative data collection to potential support for retrospectives.
S3-B1-B3	Lee, S., & Lee, J. (2018). <i>Software effort estimation using machine learning techniques: A review</i> . <i>ACM Computing Surveys</i> , 50(5), 1–37.	Review of ML for effort estimation, covering regression, ensembles, and deep learning. Provides comparative background for models like Deep-SE.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B1-B4	Whigham, P., Owen, C., & MacDonell, S. (2015). <i>A baseline model for software effort estimation</i> . ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, 40(1), 1–5.	Presents a baseline estimation model used as a comparison in later work. Important to validate advances of models like Deep-SE.
S3-B1-B5	Gupta, S., Sharma, V., & Arora, A. (2018). <i>Improving software effort estimation using hybrid models</i> . Information and Software Technology, 100, 45–59.	Explores combining supervised learning and heuristics to increase estimation accuracy. Relevant for mapping hybrid techniques adaptable to AI-supported retrospectives.
S3-B1-B6	Zhi, J., Ruhe, G., & Ali, S. (2015). <i>A practical approach for the improved accuracy of software effort estimation</i> . Empirical Software Engineering, 20(3), 760–788.	Practical approach to improve effort estimation accuracy using historical data and statistical analysis. Complements Deep-SE by integrating statistical models and ML.
S3-B1-F1	Choetkiertikul, M., Banyongrakul, P., Ragkhitwetsagul, C., Tuarob, S., Dam, H. K., & Sunetnanta, T. (2025). <i>Sprint2Vec: A Deep Characterization of Sprints in Iterative Software Development</i> . IEEE TSE, 51(1), 220–242.	Vector representation of sprints to analyze patterns and predict performance/risk. Direct evolution of DL in agile data; input for planning and retrospectives.
S3-B1-F2	Gamage, I. W., Rathnayake, R. M. U. A., & Halloluwa, T. (2024). <i>Estimating Story Points in Scrum: Balancing Accuracy and Interpretability with Explainable AI</i> . ICAC 2024, 139–144.	Combines predictive models with XAI to explain story point estimates. Targets the DL black box, easing practical adoption in Scrum.
S3-B1-F3	Kula, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2024). <i>Context-Aware Automated Sprint Plan Generation</i> . ASE 2024, 1745–1756.	Automatic sprint plan generation considering team and backlog context. Direct support for iterative planning with AI.
S3-B1-F4	Fu, M., & Tantithamthavorn, C. (2023). <i>GPT2SP: A Transformer-Based Agile Story Point Estimation Approach</i> . IEEE TSE, 49(2), 611–625.	Transformer model predicting story points from textual descriptions. State-of-the-art NLP for agile estimation.
S3-B1-F5	Tawosi, V., Moussa, R., & Sarro, F. (2024). <i>Agile Effort Estimation: Have We Solved the Problem Yet? Insights From the Replication of the GPT2SP Study</i> . SANER 2024, 1034–1041.	Replication/validation of GPT2SP, discussing generalization and robustness. Evidence on reproducibility and practical limits.
S3-B1-F6	Tawosi, V., Moussa, R., & Sarro, F. (2023). <i>Agile Effort Estimation: Have We Solved the Problem Yet? Insights From a Replication Study</i> . IEEE TSE, 49(4), 2677–2697.	Broad replication study with critical analysis of accuracy in real scenarios. Strong empirical basis for comparing estimation models.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B1-F7	Han, R., Han, W., Han, Z., Tian, Y., Chen, L., & Han, R. (2024). <i>CRSP: Emulating Human Cooperative Reasoning for Intelligible Story Point Estimation</i> . ICPC 2024, 166–177.	Proposes cooperative reasoning for more interpretable estimates. Contributes interpretability and human–AI alignment.
S3-B1-F8	Permana, B., Ferdiana, R., & Pratama, A. (2024). <i>Large Language Model Employment for Story Point Estimation Problems in Agile</i> . ICECOS 2024, 391–398.	Uses LLMs for story point estimation and discusses practical trade-offs. Relevant for LLM adoption in Scrum teams.
S3-B1-F9	Ünlü, H., Tenekeci, S., Çiftçi, C., et al. (2024). <i>Predicting Software Functional Size Using NLP: An Exploratory Case Study</i> . SEAA 2024, 188–193.	Predicts functional size with NLP, reducing manual effort. Key input for size-based estimation pipelines.
S3-B1-F10	Mittal, H. K., Arsalan, M., & Garg, P. (2024). <i>A Novel Deep Learning Model for Effective Story Point Estimation in Agile</i> . INNOCOMP 2024, 404–410.	DL for SP with preprocessing and tuning improvements. Incremental advances useful for accuracy in real contexts.
S3-B1-F11	Tawosi, V., Moussa, R., & Sarro, F. (2022). <i>On the Relationship Between Story Points and Development Effort in Agile OSS</i> . ESEM 2022, 183–194.	Investigates correlation between SP and actual effort in agile OSS. Empirical evidence to calibrate models and practices.
S3-B1-F12	Tawosi, V., Al-Subaihini, A., Moussa, R., & Sarro, F. (2022). <i>A Versatile Dataset of Agile Open Source Software Projects</i> . MSR 2022, 707–711.	Comprehensive dataset for Agile research. Essential resource for replication and benchmarking.
S3-B1-F13	Tawosi, V., Al-Subaihini, A., & Sarro, F. (2022). <i>Investigating the Effectiveness of Clustering for Story Point Estimation</i> . SANER 2022, 827–838.	Evaluates clustering to improve SP estimates. Explainable alternative to purely neural approaches.
S3-B1-F14	Phan, H., & Jannesari, A. (2022). <i>Story Point Level Classification by Text-Level Graph Neural Network</i> . NLBSE 2022, 75–78.	GNN over user story text to classify SP levels. Explores modern architectures tailored to story text.
S3-B1-F15	Rosa, W., Clark, B. K., Madachy, R., & Boehm, B. W. (2022). <i>Empirical Effort and Schedule Estimation Models for Agile Processes in the US DoD</i> . IEEE TSE, 48(8), 3117–3130.	Empirical effort and schedule models for Agile in the US DoD. Bridge between classic models and large-scale agile practice.
S3-B1-F16	Kula, E., Greuter, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2022). <i>Factors Affecting On-Time Delivery in Large-Scale Agile</i> . IEEE TSE, 48(9), 3573–3592.	Identifies factors impacting on-time delivery in large-scale Agile. Contextual variables critical for Scrum prediction models.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B2-B1	Abdelmoez, W., Kholief, M., & Elsalmy, F.M. (2012). <i>Bug Fix-Time Prediction Model Using Naïve Bayes Classifier</i> . Proc. ICCTA, 13–15.	Simple probabilistic model to predict bug fix-time. Serves as an initial basis for effort/time prediction in SE.
S3-B2-B2	Anvik, J., & Murphy, G.C. (2011). <i>Reducing the effort of bug report triage</i> . ACM TOSEM, 20(3), 1–35.	Explores automated bug triage via classification. Relates to using analytics to reduce cognitive load in agile teams.
S3-B2-B3	Anvik, J., Hiew, L., & Murphy, G.C. (2006). <i>Who should fix this bug?</i> . Proc. ICSE.	Automatic assignment of issues to developers. Direct decision support for repetitive tasks in Scrum teams.
S3-B2-B4	Bettenburg, N., Just, S., Schröter, A., Weiss, C., Premraj, R., & Zimmermann, T. (2008a). <i>What makes a good bug report?</i> . Proc. FSE, 308–318.	Analyzes quality attributes in bug reports. Empirical evidence useful for thinking about data quality metrics in retrospectives.
S3-B2-B5	Bettenburg, N., Premraj, R., & Zimmermann, T. (2008b). <i>Duplicate bug reports considered harmful... really?</i> . Proc. ICSM, 337–345.	Discusses the impact of duplicate defect reports. Contributes reflections on data noise and the need for preprocessing in AI.
S3-B2-B6	Bhattacharya, P., & Neamtiu, I. (2011). <i>Bug-fix time prediction models: can we do better?</i> . Proc. MSR, 207–210.	Evaluates predictive models for fix-time in OSS repositories. Directly related to predictive models applicable to retrospective metrics.
S3-B2-B7	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H.K., Tran, T., & Ghose, A. (2015a). <i>Characterization and prediction of issue-related risks in software projects</i> . Proc. MSR, 280–291.	Earlier work of the same authors applying repository mining to predict risks. Direct evolution of the research line underpinning S3-B2.
S3-B2-B8	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H.K., Tran, T., & Ghose, A. (2015b). <i>Predicting delays in software projects using networked classification</i> . Proc. ASE, 353–364.	Networked classification model to predict software delays. Complements S3-B2, showing an earlier approach on the same topic.
S3-B2-F1	Choetkiertikul, M., Banyongrakkul, P., Ragkhitwetsagul, C., Tuarob, S., Dam, H., & Sunetnanta, T. (2025). <i>Sprint2Vec: A Deep Characterization of Sprints in Iterative Software Development</i> . IEEE TSE, 51(1), 220–242. https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2024.3509016	Introduces vector representations of sprints for characterization and performance prediction. Direct evolution of the Choetkiertikul line, applying DL to sprint data.
S3-B2-F2	Rokoss, A., Syberg, M., Tomidei, L., Hülsing, C., Deuse, J., & Schmidt, M. (2024). <i>Case study on delivery time determination using a machine learning approach in small batch production companies</i> . J. Intell. Manuf., 35(8), 3937–3958. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10845-023-02290-2	Case study on delivery time prediction with ML. Connects deadline prediction in production processes, analogous to delay prediction in software.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B2-F3	Kula, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2024). <i>Context-Aware Automated Sprint Plan Generation</i> . Proc. ASE, 1745–1756. https://doi.org/10.1145/3691620.3695540	Automated sprint planning considering context. Direct support for agile planning decisions.
S3-B2-F4	Chen, B., Zou, W., Cai, B., Meng, Q., Liu, W., Li, P., & Chen, L. (2024). <i>An empirical study on the potential of word embedding techniques in bug report management tasks</i> . Empir. Softw. Eng., 29(5). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-024-10510-3	Explores embeddings for bug triage and classification. Expands NLP use in issue management, aligned with S3-B2.
S3-B2-F5	Kula, E., Greuter, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2023). <i>Dynamic Prediction of Delays in Software Projects using Delay Patterns and Bayesian Modeling</i> . Proc. ESEC/FSE, 1012–1023. https://doi.org/10.1145/3611643.3616328	Models software delays with historical patterns and Bayesian methods. Conceptual evolution of S3-B2’s theme.
S3-B2-F6	Pasuksmit, J., Thongtanunam, P., & Karunasekera, S. (2022). <i>Story points changes in agile iterative development</i> . Empir. Softw. Eng., 27(6). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-022-10192-9	Analyzes changes in story points in agile projects. Connects effort metrics with prediction in Agile.
S3-B2-F7	Assavakamhaenghan, N., Tanaphantaruk, W., Suwanworaboon, P., Choetkiertikul, M., & Tuarob, S. (2022). <i>Quantifying effectiveness of team recommendation for collaborative software development</i> . Autom. Softw. Eng., 29(2). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10515-022-00357-7	Evaluates automatic team recommendations for collaborative development. Supports collaborative decision-making in agile teams.
S3-B2-F8	Levy, Y., Stern, R., Sturm, A., Mordoch, A., & Bitan, Y. (2022). <i>An impact-driven approach to predict user stories instability</i> . Requirements Eng., 27(2), 231–248. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-022-00372-w	Predicts user story instability. Practical support for planning and backlog stability.
S3-B2-F9	Pasuksmit, J., Thongtanunam, P., & Karunasekera, S. (2022). <i>Towards reliable agile iterative planning via predicting documentation changes of work items</i> . Proc. MSR, 35–47. https://doi.org/10.1145/3524842.3528445	Predicts documentation changes in work items. Supports reliability in agile planning.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-B2-F10	Watson, C., Cooper, N., Palacio, D., Moran, K., & Poshyvanyk, D. (2022). <i>A Systematic Literature Review on the Use of Deep Learning in Software Engineering Research</i> . ACM TOSEM, 31(2), 1–58. https://doi.org/10.1145/3485275	Review of DL in SE. Context for how DL has been applied in software prediction and analytics.
S3-B2-F11	Kula, E., van Deursen, A., & Gousios, G. (2021). <i>Modeling team dynamics for the characterization and prediction of delays in user stories</i> . Proc. ASE, 991–1002. https://doi.org/10.1109/ASE51524.2021.9678939	Models team dynamics to predict user-story delays. Directly complements S3-B2 with a sociotechnical perspective.
S3-B2-F12	Silva, C., Galster, M., & Gilson, F. (2021). <i>Topic modeling in software engineering research</i> . Empir. Softw. Eng., 26(6). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-021-10026-0	Topic modeling in software data. Relevant as an NLP technique for bug reports/issues.
S3-B2-F13	Pasukmit, J. (2021). <i>Investigating documented information for accurate effort estimation in agile software development</i> . Proc. ESEC/FSE, 1605–1609. https://doi.org/10.1145/3468264.3473106	Effort estimation in Agile using documented information. Directly connects to effort prediction metrics.
S3-B2-F14	Tuarob, S., Assavakamhaenghan, N., Tanaphantaruk, W., Suwanworaboon, P., Hassan, S., & Choetkiertikul, M. (2021). <i>Automatic team recommendation for collaborative software development</i> . Empir. Softw. Eng., 26(4). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-021-09966-4	Automatic team recommendation. Advances collaborative support via AI.
S3-F1-B1	Hoda, R., Salleh, N., & Grundy, J. (2018). <i>The rise and evolution of agile software development</i> . IEEE Software, 35(5), 58–63.	Discusses agile evolution and its broad adoption since the 1990s. Conceptual basis to situate AI integration in the agile ecosystem. Notes: Connects to the historical panorama used in the dissertation.
S3-F1-B2	Hoda, R., & Murugesan, L. K. (2016). <i>Multi-level agile project management challenges</i> . Journal of Systems and Software, 117, 245–257.	Management challenges in self-organizing teams across multiple levels. Points to practical gaps that AI can address.
S3-F1-B3	Masood, Z., Hoda, R., & Blincoe, K. (2022). <i>Real world Scrum: A grounded theory of variations in practice</i> . IEEE TSE, 48(5), 1579–1591.	Variations of Scrum practices in real contexts. Reinforces the need for adaptive intelligent support.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-F1-B4	Hussain, W., et al. (2022). <i>How can human values be addressed in agile methods? A case study on SAFe</i> . IEEE TSE, 48(12), 5158–5175.	How to incorporate human values in agile methods (SAFe). Aligned with the focus on human values + AI in your RQ.
S3-F1-B5	Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Grundy, J., Ghose, A., & Kamei, Y. (2019). <i>Towards effective AI-powered agile project management</i> . ICSE-NIER.	Initial proposition of AI-powered APM (estimation, allocation). Pioneering intersection of AI + agile PM. (Marked as global duplicate.)
S3-F1-B5	Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Grundy, J., Ghose, A., & Kamei, Y. (2019). <i>Towards effective AI-powered agile project management</i> . ICSE-NIER.	Initial proposition of AI-powered Agile Project Management (estimation, allocation). Pioneer at the intersection of AI + agile PM. (Marked as global duplicate.)
S3-F1-B6	Fu, M., & Tantithamthavorn, C. (2023). <i>GPT2SP: A transformer-based agile story point estimation approach</i> . IEEE TSE, 49(2), 611–625.	Transformer model for story point estimation. Applied example of AI in a core APM activity.
S3-F1-F1	Takerngsaksiri, W., Pasuksmit, J., Thongtanunam, P., Tantithamthavorn, C., Zhang, R., Jiang, F., Li, J., Cook, E., Chen, K., & Wu, M. (2025). <i>Human-In-The-Loop Software Development Agents</i> . ICSE-SEIP 2025, pp. 342–352.	Proposes software development agents with humans in the loop, integrating agile practices with AI support. Aligned with the concept of augmented agile, reinforcing human–AI interaction in agile teams.
S3-F1-F2	Hoda, R. (2024). <i>Keynote on Augmented Agile: Human-centred AI-assisted Software Project Management</i> . FinanSE Workshop (ICSE 2024), pp. 17–18.	Keynote expanding the concept of augmented agile, applied to the financial sector. Relevant as dissemination of the proposal in an industrial context.
S3-F1-F3	Babulak, E., Kumar, A., Guru, D., Kudithipudi, K., Maddini, S., Gonaygunta, H., & Nadella, S. (2025). <i>Human-Centric AI Tools Into Agile Methodologies for Optimized Software Development</i> . In <i>AI-Driven Approaches for Fully Automated Smart Engineering</i> , pp. 41.	Explores human-centered AI tools applied to agile methodologies to optimize development. Directly connects to the RQ, showing practical integration cases.
S3-F1-F4	Nguyen-Duc, A., & Khanna, D. (2024). <i>Value-Based Adoption of ChatGPT in Agile Software Development: A Survey Study of Nordic Software Experts</i> . In <i>Generative AI for Effective Software Development</i> , pp. 257.	Survey study on ChatGPT adoption in agile practices, focusing on perceived value. Recent empirical evidence on real LLM usage in agile contexts.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-F1-F5	Haase, J., Walker, P. B., Bernardi, O., & Karwowski, W. (2023). <i>Get Real Get Better: A Framework for Developing Agile Program Management in the U.S. Navy Supported by Advanced Data Analytics and AI Technologies</i> , 11(6), 165.	Proposes an agile PM framework supported by analytics and AI in a military context (U.S. Navy). Contributes as an applied case of AI + Agile in a critical domain.
S3-F2-B1	Couder, J., & Ochoa, O. (2024). <i>Large Language Models, the New Scrum Masters</i> . ERAU Papers.	Argues that LLMs can take on Scrum Master roles, analyzing benefits and risks. Directly aligned with the RQ on AI substitution/support in agile roles.
S3-F2-B2	Kaleemunnisa, C., Scharff, C., Bathula, K. M., & Chen, K. (2023). <i>Analyzing Scrum Team Impediments Using NLP</i> . LNCS.	Uses NLP to identify impediments in Scrum teams. Practical evidence of AI for diagnosing problems in retrospectives.
S3-F2-B3	Young, D. L., Boyette, P., & Teske, J. (2024). <i>Generative AI Agile Assistant</i> . SPIE.	Report of a generative AI tool acting as an agile assistant. Contributes with initial practical application cases.
S3-F2-B4	Sainio, K., Abrahamsson, P., & Ahtee, T. (2024). <i>Prompt Patterns for Agile Software Project Managers: First Results</i> . LNBIP.	Proposes prompt patterns for AI use in agile management. Related to the impact of prompt engineering on effectiveness.
S3-F2-B5	Grzeszczyk, T. A. (2024). <i>Artificial intelligence and project management: an integrated approach to knowledge-based evaluation</i> . Routledge.	Book on integrating AI in project management, emphasizing knowledge-based evaluation. Provides broad theoretical foundation on AI+PM.
S3-F2-B6	Zhang, Z., Rayhan, M., Herda, T., Goisau, M., & Abrahamsson, P. (2024). <i>LLM-Based Agents for Automating User Story Quality</i> . LNBIP.	Study on LLM-based agents to improve user story quality. Relevant to supporting core retrospective activities.
S3-F2-B7	Barcaui, A., & Monat, A. (2023). <i>Who is better in project planning? Generative AI or project managers?</i> Project Leadership and Society, 4.	Comparison between project plans generated by AI and by human managers. Direct study on substitution of human roles.
S3-F2-B8	Korzynski, P., et al. (2023). <i>Generative AI as a new context for management theories: analysis of ChatGPT</i> . CEMJ, 31(1).	Analyzes the impact of ChatGPT on management theories. Provides a conceptual foundation.
S3-F2-B9	Karim Zadeh, E., Bagheri Khoulenjani, A., & Safaei, M. (2024). <i>Integrating AI for Agile Project Management: Innovations, Challenges, and Benefits</i> . IJIECM, 1(1).	Review of innovations and challenges in AI for agile management. Recent evidence directly aligned with the RQ.
S3-F2-B10	Schroder, M. (2023). <i>AutoScrum: Automating Project Planning Using Large Language Models</i> . arXiv.	Evaluates LLMs for automatic planning in Agile. Extremely relevant for triangulation with the central theme.
S3-F2-B11	Vicci, H. (2024). <i>The Impact of AI on Project Managers and Scrum Masters: A Review and Evaluation</i> . SSRN.	Review on partial automation of PM and Scrum Master roles. Provides critical view of the extent to which AI can replace humans.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-F3-B1	Kuhrmann, M., et al. (2017). <i>Hybrid software and system development in practice: waterfall, scrum, and beyond</i> . Empirical Software Engineering, 22(6), 3038–3071.	Empirical study of hybrid practices (agile + waterfall) at scale. Important to discuss hybrid scenarios where AI can support sprint planning.
S3-F3-B2	Lenarduzzi, V., Lunesu, I., & Taibi, D. (2018). <i>Analyzing forty years of software maintenance models</i> . Journal of Software: Evolution and Process, 30(7).	Review of software maintenance models. Relevant for contextualizing historical metrics in automated planning.
S3-F3-B3	Kupiainen, E., Mäntylä, M. V., & Itkonen, J. (2015). <i>Using metrics in Agile and Lean software development – A systematic literature review of industrial studies</i> . IST, 56(8), 913–929.	Mapping of metrics used in Agile/Lean. Conceptual basis to understand what data can feed AI in planning.
S3-F3-B4	Stray, V., Sjøberg, D. I. K., & Dybå, T. (2016). <i>The daily stand-up meeting: A grounded theory study</i> . Journal of Systems and Software, 114, 101–124.	Qualitative study on daily stand-ups and their effects on teams. Connects short-term agile practices with sprint planning decisions.
S3-F3-B5	Kuutila, M., Mäntylä, M. V., Claes, M., & Adams, B. (2017). <i>Using experience sampling to link software developers’ affect to their development activities</i> . ICSE.	Links developers’ emotional states with productivity. Relevant to context-aware approaches that consider human factors.
S3-F3-B6	Rodriguez, P., Markkula, J., Oivo, M., & Turula, K. (2012). <i>Survey on agile and lean usage in Finnish software industry</i> . ESEM.	Survey on Agile/Lean adoption in Finnish companies. Empirical evidence contextualizing local planning practices.
S3-F3-B7	Petersen, K., & Wohlin, C. (2010). <i>The effect of moving from a plan-driven to an incremental software development approach</i> . Empirical Software Engineering, 15(6), 654–693.	Analyzes impacts of moving from traditional to incremental/agile models. Supports discussion of how AI can mitigate risks in the transition.
S3-F3-B8	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Ghose, A., & Grundy, J. (2018). <i>Predicting delivery capability in iterative software development</i> . IEEE TSE, 44(6), 540–558.	Proposes predictive model to estimate delivery capability in agile iterations. Extremely close to the theme of sprint planning with AI.
S3-F3-B9	Misirli, A. T., & Bener, A. (2014). <i>A mapping study on Bayesian networks for software quality prediction</i> . IST, 56(8), 113–122.	Study on Bayesian networks for predicting software quality. Provides techniques applicable to sprint forecasting.
S3-F3-B10	Kitchenham, B., Budgen, D., & Brereton, P. (2015). <i>Evidence-Based Software Engineering and Systematic Reviews</i> . CRC Press.	Reference book on EBSE and systematic reviews. Provides methodological grounding for reviews applied to Agile + AI.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-F4-B1	Breque, M., De Nul, L., & Petrides, A. (2021). <i>Industry 5.0: Towards a Sustainable, Human-Centric and Resilient European Industry</i> . European Commission.	European Commission report introducing Industry 5.0, emphasizing integration of technologies like AI for sustainable, resilient, human-centered solutions. Grounds the link between AI, sustainability, and project management.
S3-F4-B2	PMI. (2021). <i>A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK® Guide), Seventh Edition</i> . Project Management Institute.	Defines eight PM performance domains: stakeholders, team, life cycle, planning, execution, delivery, measurement, and uncertainty. Essential for conceptual framing, provides methodological basis used in the review categorization.
S3-F4-B3	Choetkiertikul, M., Dam, H. K., Tran, T., Ghose, A., & Grundy, J. (2018). <i>Predicting delays in software projects using networked classification (Sprint2Vec)</i> . <i>Empirical Software Engineering</i> , 23(6), 3015–3051.	ML model to predict delays in agile tasks, introducing Sprint2Vec. Aligned with the <i>uncertainty</i> domain, connects AI with measurement and forecasting in PM.
S3-F4-B4	Nassif, A. B., Capretz, L. F., & Ho, D. (2019). <i>Towards an early software estimation using machine learning techniques</i> . <i>Journal of Systems and Software</i> , 144, 19–36.	Evaluates ML algorithms for early-stage software effort estimation, showing better results than traditional methods. Relevant to the <i>planning</i> domain, linking AI with time and effort estimation.
S3-F4-B5	Darko, A., Chan, A. P. C., & Ameyaw, E. E. (2020). <i>Artificial intelligence in the AEC industry: Scientometric analysis and future research directions</i> . <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 112, 103081.	Maps AI use in the AEC industry, identifying techniques and research gaps. Sectoral evidence on AI in PM, reinforcing S3-F4 trends.
S3-F4-F1	Barcaui, A., & Monat, A. (2023). <i>Who is better in project planning? Generative artificial intelligence or project managers?</i> Project Leadership and Society.	Compares project plans generated by GPT-4 versus human PMs. Direct evidence on AI performance in project planning.
S3-F4-F2	Felicetti, A. M., Cimino, A., Mazzoleni, A., & al. (2024). <i>Artificial intelligence and project management: An empirical investigation on the appropriation of generative chatbots by project managers</i> . <i>Journal of Innovation & Knowledge</i> .	Empirical study of generative chatbot adoption by PMs. Shows real appropriation of LLMs in PM routines.
S3-F4-F3	Prasetyo, M. L., Peranginangin, R. A., Martinovic, N., & al. (2025). <i>Artificial intelligence in open innovation project management: A systematic literature review</i> . <i>Journal of Open Innovation</i> .	SLR mapping technologies, applications, and integration requirements of AI in PM. Updated synthesis of AI+PM; dialogues with S3-F4 findings.

ID	Reference	Summary /brief
S3-F4-F4	Vergara, D., del Bosque, A., Lampropoulos, G., & al. (2025). <i>Trends and applications of artificial intelligence in project management</i> . Electronics.	Survey of AI trends and applications in PM. Application overview aligned with the RQ.
S3-F4-F5	Mohammad, A., & Chirchir, B. (2024). <i>Challenges of integrating artificial intelligence in software project planning: a systematic literature review</i> . Digital.	SLR focused on challenges of integrating AI into software project planning. Identifies barriers/risks—inputs for framework requirements.
S3-F4-F6	Adamantiadou, D. S., & Tsiromis, L. (2025). <i>Leveraging artificial intelligence in project management: A systematic review of applications, challenges, and future directions</i> . Computers.	Broad review of AI applications and challenges in PM. Triangulates with S3-F4 scope and your RQ.
S3-F4-F7	Aamer, A., Zadeh, A., Mali, P., & Bolick, C. (2025). <i>Emerging technologies and principle-based project management: a systematic literature review and research agenda</i> . Management Review Quarterly.	SLR on emerging technologies (including AI) and principle-based PM. Links AI to PMBOK 7 performance/value domains.
S3-F4-F8	Haase, J., Walker, P. B., Berardi, O., & Karwowski, W. (2023). <i>Get Real Get Better: A framework for developing agile program management in the U.S. Navy supported by advanced data analytics and AI</i> . Technologies.	Agile PM framework supported by analytics/AI in a military context. Robust applied case (program/portfolio + AI).
S3-F4-F9	Hughes, L., Mavi, R. K., Aghajani, M., & al. (2025). <i>Impact of artificial intelligence on project management (PM): Multi-expert perspectives toward PM2030</i> . Journal of Innovation & Knowledge.	Delphi/multi-expert perspectives on the future of AI in PM toward 2030. Prospective evidence for impact discussions.
S3-F4-F10	Kalogiannidis, S., Kalfas, D., Pappaevangelou, O., & al. (2024). <i>The role of AI in predictive risk assessment for business continuity</i> . Risks.	AI use for predictive risk assessment and business continuity. Aligned with risk management/measurement (PMBOK 7).
S3-F4-F11	Babulak, E., Kumar, A., Guru, D., & al. (2025). <i>Human-Centric AI Tools Into Agile Methodologies for Optimized Software Development</i> . In: <i>AI-Driven Approaches for Fully Automated Smart Engineering</i> .	Human-centered AI tools applied to agile methodologies. Direct alignment with AI+Agile (human-centered).

S3-F4- F12	Nguyen-Duc, A., & Khanna, D. (2024). <i>Value-Based Adoption of ChatGPT in Agile Software Development: A Survey Study of Nordic Experts</i> . In: <i>Generative AI for Effective Software Development</i> .	Survey on value-based adoption of ChatGPT in Agile. Recent empirical evidence of LLM use in Agile.
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Grey literature is composed of knowledge artifacts that are not products of peer-review processes characteristic of publication in scientific journals.

Search string. A *string* based on the *snowballing* stage was used:

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("AI" OR "Artificial Intelligence" OR "Machine Learning")
AND
("Agile" OR "Agile Methodologies" OR "Scrum" OR "Scrum Framework")
AND
("Technical Report" OR "White Paper" OR "Dissertation" OR "Thesis"
OR "Blog" OR "Tweet" OR "Forum Post" OR "Grey Literature")
AND
(site:medium.com OR site:stackoverflow.com OR site:scrum.org OR site:gov OR site:edu OR site:org)
```

Inclusion criteria.

- Application of AI in agile environments (Scrum and the like);
- Last 5 years; texts in Portuguese or English;
- Sources classifiable into Tiers 1–3.

Exclusion criteria.

- Absence of direct AI–agile methods relationship;
- Purely opinion-based texts without practical examples/case studies;
- Duplicates or substantially redundant content.

Table 5: General summary of grey literature search results

Source	Total Found	Selected
Medium (general)	60	8
Atlassian / IBM / McKinsey	12	3
StackOverflow / Reddit	3	0
Medium (AI-powered tools)	1	1
Institutional sites (.org)	30	3
Overall Total	106	15

Table 6: Selection of relevant technical blogs (examples)

Source / Link	Title	Relevance to this study
Medium	Unleashing the Power of AI in Scrum	AI prompts applicable to retrospectives.
Medium	Agile Methodology in the Age of AI	Theoretical and contextual foundation.
Medium	How AI Is Reshaping the Agile Sprint Cycle	Practical impacts of AI on the agile cycle.

Source / Link	Title	Relevance to this study
Medium	AI-Powered Agility in the Software Industry	Corporate use cases.
Medium	Why AI Can't Replace a Scrum Master	Limitations of AI in Scrum.
Medium	Improve Project Management with AI	General applications in agile environments.
Medium	Value of Retrospectives	Strategic role of retrospectives.
Medium	How I Automated Team Emotions with GPT	Analysis of team emotions with AI.

Table 7: Selection of institutional/technical sources (examples)

Source / Link	Title	Relevance to this study
Atlassian	MyAgileCopilot – ChatGPT for agile backlog	AI-powered tool applicable to Scrum practices.
McKinsey	A New Management Science for Technology Delivery	Foundation for agile management with AI.
Atlassian	AI Tools for Ticket Categorization	Use of AI in agile workflows with Jira.
IEEE	Application of Data Analytics Techniques for Decision Making	AI-based methods applicable to continuous improvement.
arXiv	A Case for More Data-informed Retrospective Activities	Direct proposal for data-driven retrospectives.

Interview Protocol for the Qualitative Study

This appendix presents the interview protocol used in the qualitative stage of the study. The goal was to deepen the practical understanding of the use of Artificial Intelligence in Scrum retrospectives by capturing perceptions from industry and academic professionals regarding challenges, opportunities, and critical adoption factors. The protocol was structured into thematic blocks, each with open-ended questions, as detailed in Table 8.

Table 8: Thematic blocks and open-ended questions for the qualitative interviews

Block	Questions
1 – Experience with Scrum retrospectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How would you describe your experience with agile retrospectives in Scrum teams? - Which formats or activities do you usually use in retrospectives? - What are the main challenges you face when running these retrospectives? - What concrete impacts have you noticed on teams after effective retrospectives?
2 – Knowledge and use of AI in agile environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe situations in which you have encountered the use of AI in agile development contexts. - How do you view the role of AI in supporting Scrum teams? - In which specific aspects of the Scrum framework could AI provide the most value (e.g., data analysis, action suggestions, issue prioritization)?
3 – Decision support in retrospectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you used any tool (with or without AI) that provided analytical support during retrospectives? How did it assist decision-making? - Describe how you believe AI-based tools could support decision-making in retrospectives. - What kinds of recommendations or analyses do you consider useful during this ceremony?
4 – Barriers and enablers for AI adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which factors could hinder the adoption of an AI-based tool in retrospectives? - Which elements could facilitate this adoption in agile teams?
5 – Trust and transparency in AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What would be your expectations regarding transparency and explainability of the recommendations made by an AI tool during a retrospective? - How could the introduction of AI impact team members' trust in the process and in each other? What concerns might arise and how could they be mitigated?
6 – Role of the human facilitator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you see the interaction between the human facilitator and the AI tool? - What do you consider essential to remain the responsibility of the human facilitator?
7 – Ideal scenarios for AI use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In what types of retrospectives (e.g., newly formed teams, high-performance teams, post-incident) do you believe AI would be most useful? - In which contexts does AI tend to be most beneficial (regular meetings, crisis moments, organizational changes, growth phases)? Why?

Interview Data and Open Coding Results

This appendix provides transparency regarding the qualitative data collected through semi-structured interviews.

Question	Response
<p>How would you describe your experience with agile retrospectives in Scrum teams?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Great experience" - "useful, informative and it should not be ignored." - My experiences have differed based on where geographically my teams are located. For most teams in the North America, or western hemisphere areas my experiences have been positive; I've seen retro work to not only improve team practices but also team morale. For other geographies I've found it more difficult for team members to open up about recommending any changes - I've been on both sides of retrospectives, both as an individual contributor and as a manager. Early in my career, the most productive retrospectives were always more direct, without much polish in the feedback, but all feedback based on reality. - I've participated in Scrum teams since 2009. In 2011 I became a Scrum Master. I appreciate the interactive nature of the process, the team participation, and especially the focus on communication. I also find the self organizing nature beneficial to the team. - I have extensive experience leading agile retrospectives in Scrum teams, acting both as a facilitator and contributing as a team member. - Often, they are extremely rigid and non-objective, causing a lot of time to be wasted unnecessarily. - Quite a bit of experience. I have been working with agile teams for the past 15 years. As a Project Manager I have facilitated and participated in retrospectives for the teams I managed quite frequently. - I worked for a few years as a Product Owner on teams under construction, even with highly mature teams, and the younger the team, the more important the process adjustment and behavior review meetings were. - I find them to be moderately useful. On a good team, members go beyond the typical kudos or shoutouts and post insightful questions and offer constructive criticism. However, with poor management or bad teams I find these are rarely useful. - They are a necessary part of every healthy team. - almost none, its the most forgotten ceremony so we usually don't do it by the book every 2 weeks - Good - In my experience, teams using agile methodology end up becoming more organized, with more autonomy, more frequent deliveries, and better structured processes. - Retrospectives are essential for the continuous improvement of the team and the project, but this depends largely on the team's maturity and how they use the meeting. I've had experiences where the retrospective only brought up positive points, when in fact there were several negative points to be reviewed, which in the long run caused a lot of friction within the team. Overall, my experience with retrospectives has always been positive; even with difficult moments, the outcome is always learning and an opportunity for improvement, and/or recognition for the work done. - Retrospectives have evolved throughout different team sizes but it seemed to be invaluable for every project I worked on that utilized them - It's always the same board style with four sections: positive points, negative points, action points, and kudos. I feel like doing the entire sprint is unnecessary. I believe it's okay to do every other sprint, especially on teams where sprints are two weeks long. However, I worked on a team where the scrum master did different types of retrospectives, some more interactive and others less so. - I have been on several teams that do a retrospective either once a month, or twice a month.

Question	Response
<p>What formats or dynamics do you usually use during retrospectives?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization and discussion of team metrics; Star, Stop, Continue; - The Ship sailing image which asks 4 questions 1. Winds in our sails (What went well). 2. Anchors (things holding us back/Blockers) 3. Land/Sea (foreseeing any potential issues) 4. What can be done better. - Following a standard agenda where we highlight accomplishments as well as practices that are working well and the team's hard work and also difficulties that we've faced where we try to discuss potential solutions together. I also like to give the team a space toward the end where we can merely say anything we want to say. - We used a website with several retrospective templates, one that showed how the team was performing, what was holding the team back, what people liked about the team, a dynamic that facilitated direct feedback between members, and at the end, we created a list of improvements (which we could hardly keep track of during the sprints). - "On some teams we've gone over our output by examining the board and velocity to determine where we could improve. - For the last five years plus we've used a board with columns to talk about what went well, what didn't go well, and what we could improve. - Those questions produce a list of action items for folks to work on." - Defining the format and dynamics of a retrospective depends on the size of the team, the stage of development within the Tuckman model, the time available for the ceremony, and the participants' status (in-person or remote). A retrospective can use a simple format like "Good, Bad, How to Improve" or explore fun formats like the Three Little Pigs model or the Hot Air Balloon model to promote engagement or help the team think outside the box to identify problems. - Retrospective chart - "The most common dynamics are: What we did well; What we did badly; What needs to change; What to improve. I also used a lot: Start; Stop; Continue. And some dynamics of Future expectations: Like the hot air balloon dynamics." - The most common dynamic was Start, Stop, Continue. It helped teams achieve more points without having to appoint people. - For the past 10+ years these calls to me have been phone/video calls based and are captured using some web based tool. - There are multiple formats to try and keep things fresh and new for the team but at the core of it, I want to understand what's going well, what can be and action items (with owners) for the team. - usually websites that offer templates of topics to discuss, for example: dos, don'ts and action items - FigJam board, EasyRetro - "I usually use a board with several columns, where participants add cards to each column. The columns are usually: Shoutouts, What went well? Keep Doing, What was wack?, What to Change, and Next Steps - Action Items. After cards have been added to each column, I read them all, opening the floor for discussion with the entire team." - It really depends on the team's needs. I personally find it very helpful to create a visual representation of where we are and where we want to go, to visually clarify the points that are holding us back and those that are helping us reach the final goal. I feel this captures people's minds better than just a simple "liked, learned, and lacked" chart. However, I also think it depends on the team's maturity; I think these cases are better for teams that are just starting out or are less mature. It's also very important to create a "contract" at the beginning of meetings, emphasizing the meeting's principles: that it is a safe, welcoming place, focused on problem-solving. - Different formats, usually in the form of 'Start Stop Continue' or 'Kudos What Went Well, What to Improve, Action Items'; Previously used sticky notes on a white board but now we've been using FigJam - "Currently, my team only uses the style that I believe is the most standard: positive points, negative points, action points, and kudos." - Usually I have used some version of figma or lucid chart. Members of the team can add comments and then the team discusses the comments.

Question	Response
<p>What are the main challenges you face when conducting these retrospectives?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make participants actually bring up the points of greatest friction and those that have the greatest potential to bring results to the team. - team - Keeping team members focused on the conversation. It's far too easy to be distracted by work when we are conducting retros virtually - As a manager, my biggest difficulty was getting everyone present to participate in the retro, and having a certain naturalness in following the process. Most of the time, I ended up being a bit robotic. - None really. The sprint is fresh in people's minds. Perhaps forgetting something until after the retro is over? - Create a safe environment for people to contribute effectively, ensure that discussions focus on problems and not on people, and direct discussions toward finding solutions that improve future iterations rather than looking for someone to blame for the unsatisfactory results of the iteration under review. - Do not fall into operationality and related matters - Create a safe environment for people to open up about their problems. Get everyone involved. Bring external leaders (clients) into the dynamic, understanding that they are part of the team. Leave with realistic actions that can be executed as soon as the dynamic is over - Bring participants' focus to that moment, reminding them how important it is for their growth as a team. - The willingness of team members to participate fully - Figuring out how/if we should involve the client teams. When a client team is engaged and collaborative, then it is fantastic. However, if the team isn't able to speak freely or openly about issues with the client in the room then we need to have it separate. - establishing a secure environment where people feel safe to talk without filters but at the same time keeping it professional without holding grudges or taking it personal - Keeping everyone engaged and actively participating are some of the challenges - Participants may be shy about adding topics to columns, or not engaging in discussions, resulting in the same people always interacting. - People aren't truly transparent. Some teams create a culture of pretending everything is fine. Catching a team like this halfway makes it very difficult to undo this behavior. Furthermore, bringing conflicts and issues to the table can be complicated because emotions can flare, so it's important to have the contract clearly spelled out with the team. - Getting retrospectives scheduled on a regular basis, getting everyone to participate and feel comfortable enough to respond, time-boxing discussions - Team engagement to address negative points. Besides that, I believe another issue is the person assigned to perform the action item actually completing it, which is always postponed to the next sprint. - It can be challenging to facilitate an open environment where people feel comfortable bringing up any problem areas or areas that can be improved.

Question	Response
<p>What concrete impacts have you noticed in the teams after effective retrospectives?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teams correct friction points and gain greater delivery speed, including a better atmosphere among members. - change in strategy while working or better approach to project management - An improved sense of camaraderie and togetherness - Teams become more introspective and critical of their own work, feedback between members is easier at this time and the improvement process continues. - "Mostly we fix the things we determine we can improve. Not all of them, but usually the things that can make the biggest impact. - - Freeing people from busy work related to process is usually the biggest thing I've seen. Often times automating some sort of process results in big gains, like getting CI/CD in a good spot." - Improved team processes, improved communication between team members, breaking down silos in multidisciplinary teams or teams made up of members from different organizations, increased productivity and velocity - After a few reviews, I noticed that the team developed better after shorter and more objective reviews. - "Increased communication between people. - Freedom to bring up problems. - The feeling of ""taking the elephant out of the room"". - Sense of belonging and team commitment" - Increased team collaboration and communication and improved interpersonal relationships within the team. - Incremental refinements on delivery process and overall work flow. Client communication improvements based on team observations. - Worst case, the team is generally less stressful. Best case, the team is more productive and the leadership team is able to gain insight into issues that we weren't aware the team was having. - the action items were followed, and the team was actively conscious about making it happen - Following up on action items sends a positive signal to the team - Improved communication, a more united team, and improvements in processes that were not so clear after they were discussed in the retro. - The peace of mind of being able to address a problem after it's been identified and an action plan has been created. For example, if someone was late for three consecutive days, and the action plan was for them to always arrive on time, they don't wait until the next retrospective to address it, but rather address it as soon as the problem is noticed. - action items that had DRIs were acted upon, improved morale especially when road-blocks are eliminated as a result of feedback - Improved communication and partnership between colleagues - I think retrospectives help bring the team together and occasionally process changes can be surfaced.

Question	Response
<p>In what situations have you come across the use of AI in agile development contexts?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For technical consultations and code review only - Software Development, Requirements gathering - When trying to get a new UI quickly in front of people to iterate on; when investigating difficult defects to solve; when searching for best practices or alternate perspectives quickly - Cursor, chatgpt search, fake data generation - None - I explored the use of artificial intelligence in developing reports and monitoring charts, in developing the code itself, creating test scenarios, and as a tool for brainstorming and organizing ideas. - In reviews, retrospectives and plannings - In software development experiments using tools like Cursor AI to complete tasks end-to-end, quickly executing commands while keeping programmers in the loop. We're also testing some tools to help analyze data from the team's workflow in Jira for insights into metrics and areas for improvement. - Today it is very close to the PO and SM roles, which can be used to accelerate the unfolding of the team's needs in terms of US or helping the SM in search of more modern means to motivate and engage the team to obtain the expected result. - My experience has been the use of AI to construct and debug code in the development context. However, I am just starting to see the use of AI generated transcripts used to make it easier to search for requirements hidden within client zoom meetings. - Have seen a couple uses for AI in development so far: Coding: AI is incredibly useful for quickly prototyping ideas. It will typically do a good job of getting you 85% there and the last 15% usually development, making summaries, and translation of requirements - Developers are using AI coding tools like Cursor and Github Copilot. Meetings are being transcribed by AI. Copilots are being used to create JIRA stories. - To help create the board, and help make a summary/transcript of the meeting. - Using sites like chatgpt: think about dynamics according to the individual characteristics of a team and create user stories. - Summarizing team surveys for retrospectives; summarizing jira ticket comments - code completion and code/framework questions - AI is especially helpful in summarizing meetings and also providing a first approach to a challenging problem or bug.

Question	Response
How do you perceive the role of AI in supporting Scrum teams?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I don't have experience using AI in these contexts to offer an opinion. But from a perspective, I believe it could help summarize and cluster the points raised by team members and propose action plans to address them. - heavy use - I feel there's a place for AI tools like any other tool - team members just need education and experience to know how best to leverage it - I didn't stop to think about it much. - I could see using it to build summaries of a spring so we make sure to hit on everything done during a sprint. Perhaps use it to generate things to improve? - There is great potential for artificial intelligence to support Scrum teams, but so far I have only experienced it in terms of assisting with data analysis and reporting. - I see an extremely important role in reviewing task descriptions, since tasks are often poorly budgeted due to a lack of information in the task descriptions. - AI can play a valuable and evolving role in supporting Scrum teams by enhancing productivity, decision-making, and collaboration together with the expertise of the supporting team - The main advantage of using AI is the speed of building artifacts that the team can work on, or even artifacts that can serve as a basis for the team. - From an engineering perspective the role of AI has provided a large increase in efficiencies from code autocompletes, code generation, test case generation, even just finding code segments with search enhancements. - Currently as a support and enabler/velocity increaser. - not essential, but a nice to have - AI can analyze past sprint data and project history to provide more accurate estimates for sprint planning and setting more realistic goals. - It can make some repetitive tasks easier, like creating a meeting summary or collecting action items. - It can be very useful for assisting with specific tasks, such as those mentioned above. I know there are also AIs that can assist with code review. I believe AI has a significant role to play in Scrum. - I view AI as a complementary force that enhances team productivity while maintaining the human elements essential to agile principles like collaboration and adaptation. - So far, in addition to code, I know that my former scrum master sometimes used it to ask for retrospective tips to get out of the standard format.

Question	Response
<p>In which specific aspects of the Scrum framework could AI provide the most value (e.g., data analysis, action suggestions, problem prioritization)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis and action suggestions. In that order. - problem/requirement analysis, testing - rapid development and iteration - I believe that the AI's suggestions are all valid, it's up to the team to have self-knowledge and be able to separate the value of the suggestions and apply them on a daily basis. - Summarization, recommendations, analyzing complexity (story points) to correlate estimated vs actual complexity. That's a tough one to pull out of the data unless you document the problems, I believe. - Data analysis, reporting, problem analysis, and test scenario proposal - Prioritization and task description - I think it can analyze velocity, cycle times, and burndown charts bringing insights. Also detect deviations from sprint planning, and search for inefficiencies in workflow. In a quality analysis context, it can identify gaps in test coverage as well. - - - The obvious answer is in code generation speed and test generation speed. However, I think an overlooked opportunity is the use of AI to find ticket dependencies. Too often we create hundreds of tickets that aren't properly linked or we don't see the dependencies. This creates logjams when an unknown dependency is finally acknowledged. If an AI tool was used to review ticket language to help identify these dependencies we could have a much better sense of priority and ticket backlog order. - I think this area is going to evolve rather quickly so right now it's largely with the LLM based AI such as coding / documentation. I think it will begin to move into all parts of Scrum though. - eliciting requirements and translation - AI powered tools can automate tasks like backlog updates, status tracking, and progress reporting, freeing up team members to focus on development. - Action suggestions, and I believe data analysis as well, although I haven't used it for that purpose yet. - Meeting agendas, suggestions for improvement actions based on what is mentioned in retrospectives, analysis of information about PRs (amount of rework, change requests, etc.), definition of estimates based on past estimates. - Summarizing discussions, data analysis for team surveys - data analysis, action suggestions - I think AI is most useful in data analysis and action suggestion.

Question	Response
<p>Have you ever used any tool (with or without AI) that offered analytical support during retrospectives? How did it assist decision-making?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I've never used it. - Survey forms. We monitored the results and adjusted accordingly. - none - No - None - No. All the retrospectives I've led have been facilitated and analyzed by a human component. The only approximate use of artificial intelligence I've ever made in retrospectives was for word cloud generation. - I've never used it - No :(- Yes, I used a project management tool bundled with artificial intelligence to analyze sentiment and identify patterns in team comments during retrospectives. In prioritizing actions: Providing a clear overview of areas requiring immediate attention, based on objective data. - None - I don't think so - never - None - I didn't actually use it, I saw others using it, and it helped when listing action items at the end of the meeting, based on what was discussed. - None of them provide analytical support, but I've used sites like funretrospective to think about dynamics and the easyretro site to conduct online retros. - Other than using our internal Fuel iX to summarize team surveys, I have not used any tool - Never - I have not!

Question	Response
<p>How do you think AI-based tools could support decision-making in retrospectives?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing a summary of the main problems identified - It can foresee certain potential issues - basically by highlighting all of the issues being discussed (note-taking) and applying some analysis on how those issues should be prioritized - I think the decision making should be up to the team, it can help by quickly bringing some suggestions - Maybe? I'm not sure? I haven't considered using AI for this particular area but I do like the idea of it! - There is potential to assist in the agglutination and ordering of problems after initial inputs, in prioritizing and suggesting solutions to prioritized problems. - From the deliveries of the sprints, as well as, review of the tasks - It depends: I see it being used in two places: 1) Before the retrospective: seeking insights through analysis of sprint data: card writing patterns, quality of refinement, acceptance criteria. It could analyze the team's flow metrics and bring information to compose the retro. 2) During the dynamic, I think it could analyze the content of the cards that the team is bringing, find patterns, use previous retros as data and measure the evolution and effectiveness of the team's retros. - "Scenario Simulation: Allows the team to simulate different approaches to problems, predicting the potential outcomes of each. - Action Personalization: Personalized recommendations for each team member, based on their strengths, weaknesses, and previous contributions." - Pattern recognition. Using AI to analyze cards created during retrospectives could identify issues or positive items that occur over time. - I'm not sure how many decisions are being made as part of a retrospective. Typically they're more about learning and understanding and then there are maybe some aspects of action items that are based on decision making. I think AI could be helpful if it was providing insightful data that the team could use that supplements how teams are feeling are observing. - giving suggestions and insights based on the input - AI excels at uncovering recurring issues, bottlenecks, and trends across sprints that might be missed in traditional retrospectives. - I think it can help to raise options and weigh the pros and cons, but I think the final decision should be made by the team. - I believe they can help by understanding the team's main strengths and weaknesses and identifying possible action points. However, I don't think AI would go much further than what a SM is already capable of and perceives individually in each meeting; perhaps it would just be an "automated" way of reaching the same conclusions. It might be a good tool for overworked SMs, but I don't think that's a good perspective either, lol. I believe the best use of AI would be to generate insights about meetings as a whole, understand changes between them, and assess whether retrospectives are actually productive and generating improvements for the team. - it can probably summarize information for easier decision making and providing metrics - Currently I can't see her making decisions beyond giving tips on what are possible good action items to be created. - I think it could be helpful to use it to summarize positive feedback to input into a reporting framework for promotions, and also potentially it could provide some prompts to inspire more constructive feedback?

Question	Response
<p>What types of recommendations or analyses do you find useful during this ceremony?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clustering of problems raised by team members; detecting common symptoms and identifying root causes within the team - help to build a psychologically safe environment to encourage everyone to speak - Summary of past retrospectives, how many sprints the team has complained about the same problem, and suggestions for actions to be taken. - It usually comes down to communication with client teams and how we can get them to make decisions faster or answer questions more quickly. - Artificial intelligence that helps group and organize problems, prioritize and propose solutions. - I think it's valid to analyze the sprint's performance as a team, evaluating the positive and negative points as well as its impact on the sprint's development. - Search for problem patterns in the team by reviewing previous data from the retrospectives. Also understand evolution and maturity. Analyze the workflow and good practices of agile development and find dysfunctions in flow management and metrics. Also look for patterns of team dissatisfaction that can lead to a drop in NPS - "Areas for Improvement: Clear identification of areas requiring attention, accompanied by practical suggestions for improvement. - Impact of Actions: Analysis of the impact of decisions made in previous retrospectives to assess the effectiveness of the measures implemented." - A general summary is usually sufficient. - I think a scorecard of how the team did could be interesting with objective metrics to look into. I think another area could be for the AI to group together common themes from the team with potential action items if it has enough context - regarding the team - AI can automatically suggest action items based on retrospective discussions, assign them to team members, send reminders, and track their progress. This ensures that agreed-upon improvements are followed through and don't fall through the cracks. - Analysis of the team's pain points and suggestions for improvements. - Recommend what can be done to solve a problem. Identify the most frequently cited positive and negative points. Review the retrospectives, identify what changed between each retrospective, and whether the problems were actually resolved. - recommend immediate action items - give tips on what are possible good action items to be created

Question	Response
<p>What factors could hinder the adoption of an AI-based tool in retrospectives?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tools that are not practical to use - Licensing costs, project needs/size, client/company size - any type of listening device could alter the perceived safety of the retro - AI suggests impossible things, not knowing the product as a whole - Expense, inconsistency, poor recommendations, hallucinating - Fear that data analyzed by artificial intelligence will be used for purposes other than retrospective - Lack of openness to AI in companies, as well as a lack of openness to new technologies or very rigid processes - I'm sorry for not bringing solid experiences in use, but something that comes to mind is the generation of resistance from the team due to the low reliability of the generated data. I see a time for improvement and adaptation that the team needs to be willing to go through. - "Security and Privacy Concerns: Concerns about protecting sensitive data and complying with privacy regulations (e.g., LGPD, GDPR). - Lack of AI Knowledge: Difficulty understanding the value added by AI technology and uncertainty about how AI can improve retrospective processes." - Cost - Potential privacy issues/concerns - not sure - AI-powered retrospectives may involve collecting and analyzing sensitive data from team members, raising privacy concerns. - Everyone must agree that the tool should be used, and the tool must be reliable, with a guarantee of data security. - Confidentiality and security concerns regarding projects and people. Retrospectives can reveal details, flaws, and defects that shouldn't be disclosed outside the team. - learning curve and consistency of tool usage - If what is written by my team is feeding and "teaching" the AI, which depending on the company can be a very negative point, making the AI have to have a mode in which this does not happen. - I think people would be interested in using AI in retrospectives. I suppose any learning curve could hinder its adoption. Additionally if it because too automated it would take the human aspect that is valuable in a retrospective away.

Question	Response
<p>What elements could facilitate this adoption in agile teams?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with tools widely used for these ceremonies. Ex: Figma - proof that it helps. Seeing and then believing - Quick response, efficient suggestions, outsourcing the work that no one likes to do - Proof of an empowered team based on feedback from the team. - Easy integration with multiple tools used to conduct retrospectives, ability to analyze data and provide quick responses so as not to compromise the ceremony's timebox - Something that is not a priority in the process, some tool that can be inserted or removed from the process at any time. Also, I think it would be interesting to have something that is quick to insert into sprints, without too much bureaucracy. - Use data from previous sprints to train the method and arrive at the dynamics more accurately. Be clear about what is expected of the tool, don't leave too much open, "shoot in all directions", perhaps having the idea of MVP here is important, start small and evolve. A direction would help with confidence - Demonstration of added value, integration with existing tools, ongoing training and support, and security and compliance guarantees - Managerial willingness. - Outsized benefit/value in addition to delegating responsibilities to AI that people don't want to do - not sure - Data scattered across different systems and formats can be integrated and fed into an AI tool. - A tool that has already been tested and used by other teams in the company can make it easier to adapt. - No idea - awareness and exposure to tools that we can actually use, ability of tools to accept different file formats that we can upload

Question	Response
<p>What are your expectations regarding the transparency and explainability of AI-generated recommendations during a retrospective?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - View of content generated only for the team at the moment. No history or reports to other layers that could jeopardize the team's confidence when exposing problems and day-to-day situations. - It should only use the current/exiting project information and retro template created by a delivery practice lead. - all generated text/ideas must be fully accessible by all team members at the same time - I hope the AI generates really useful and possible suggestions. - High. If the quality isn't there these tools would be useless. We're going to know if the recommendations are good or not. - The terms of use of data and its response are essential, as is transparency about how artificial intelligence is trained. - Something that conveys objectivity, as well as the real problems faced by the team during the sprint - Always keep the team in control, the tool comes to help bring insights and take the burden off the team, but for this teams should understand the rationale behind any AI suggestion, work on improving the quality of recommendations and learning capacity. - I hope that AI recommendations will be seamlessly integrated into the retrospective process, not overriding human reflection but complementing it. - I have none presently - Rules around how it'll be used/not used. - that these recommendations are actually real and tested beforehand, and not just made up to fulfill an answer - AI can generate reports summarizing the team's performance during the sprint, including key achievements, challenges, and areas for improvement. - I expect concise recommendations, and it would be nice to have the source where the AI got this information from. - It would be very interesting to understand the line of thought both to understand a new point of view and to identify potential misconceptions about the tool. - clearly distinguish between factual data-driven insights and predictive or speculative recommendations, trace back its recommendations to specific sprint events or metrics - "Considering the team: Who in the company will be able to see this analysis?" - Considering the company: Is the AI having access to confidential information?" - I am usually very happy with the explanations that Ai gives, and offering multiple solutions could be beneficial as well as then the participants can choose.

Question	Response
<p>In your view, how might introducing an AI-based tool during retrospectives affect team members' trust in the process and in each other? What concerns might arise, and how could they be addressed or mitigated within agile teams?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I believe it doesn't affect internal trust. It can speed up the analysis of issues raised and help identify possible root causes and proposed solutions. The concern that may arise is the confidentiality of information shared by the team. It's crucial that this information isn't exposed and/or shared with other company employees. - It can highlight certain things that we as humans cannot see or ignore. - I think AI-tools in retrospectives will at first seem intrusive thus causing people to refrain from speaking. Over time, perhaps that will fade - supervisors of teams e.g. company CEOs and such should go out of their way to assure teams that the AI tool is not spying - I think confidence in the process increases, since AI tends to have an unbiased view, the concern is not to overuse AI knowing that it is just a suggestion tool, the improvement comes from the team understanding the process and applying the improvements on a daily basis. - As long as the tools aren't used to point fingers and provide constructive outputs I think they could be useful. - One concern would be the subsequent misuse of feedback information, which could be mitigated by transparency of use. Another concern could be related to the feasibility of the proposed actions and their actual effectiveness within the team context, which could be mitigated by reinforcing the right to challenge and review any results proposed by artificial intelligence. - Questions may arise about who did what during the sprint, which can lead to side conversations within the team. I also believe that first impressions carry the most weight, so if the AI isn't accurate the first time, teams will stop using it. - The team's trust in the method will be promoted, maintained or shaken according to the use and power we give the tool. An incremental view of use is necessary, for a gradual gain in trust. Once the team does not believe in the data source or perceives erroneous insights, my concern is not to adopt it at all, and to reflect little on the scope of its contribution when an error arises along the way. To mitigate this, I like the culture of experimentation in small contexts. Testing little by little in isolated scenarios/topics to control the damage/gain. Another way to mitigate this is to include the team as part of the construction of this method, not leaving all the work to the Scrum Master/Agile Coach to manage. Use and improvement must be a challenge for the entire team. - "Impact on Trust: - Positive: AI can increase trust by providing objective, data-driven insights, as long as its methodology is transparent. - Negative: If poorly implemented, it can generate distrust if recommendations are perceived as imposing or not aligned with the team's reality." - I think it depends on its usage. If it is analyzing language for feedback patterns, I don't see this as an avenue for degraded trust in the process. If, however, retrospectives input were meant to be anonymous but AI tools breached that anonymity this would severely degrade trust and reduce true input from the team. - I think retrospectives are a uniquely human and intimate private setting for folks to get stuff off their chest. I think if AI was to be introduced it would need to be in a subtle way so that it wasn't taking away from that. - maybe someone responsible for operating the tool could manipulate the retro input and this would generate a completely different output? maybe trusting the ai tool would also be of concern: did it generate a real response, or did it just make up this answer based on nothing? - AI can identify patterns and trends that might not be obvious to humans, providing deeper insights and suggesting actionable recommendations for improvement, which can increase confidence in the process's effectiveness. - I don't see how it could affect trust among team members, but I do see it affecting trust in the process, depending on the team's acceptance of the tool itself and its suggestions. The team may end up disregarding the AI's suggestions, and it could end up wasting time. - If the tool identifies a problem that the team (one with limited maturity) doesn't want to see, it will likely be disregarded and downplayed. Adopting such a tool requires a SM who can utilize the insights without relying entirely on it and make sound judgments about the suggestions. - Over-reliance on AI recommendations - Encourage team members to critically evaluate AI suggestions - I think that open communication would help mitigate any concerns around trust and also help mitigate issues. If AI were used in retros in a way that furthered this open communication I think it would keep these issues from occurring.

Question	Response
<p>How do you see the interaction between the human facilitator and the AI tool?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asking AI to perform analyses and/or suggest solutions. You can also request the construction of boards for dynamics, etc. - As a moderator - I see the AI tool as just that - a tool, not a facilitator. It can try to glean insights and display them to all team members simultaneously - Yes - I would expect an integration with our toolchain. E.G. access to our git repo and our ticketing system so it can set up a correlation between the two to formulate feedback. It may also need access to our Slack and document repositories so we can capture free form conversations around daily activity and more formalized outputs like documents created as a result of a spike. - The facilitator uses artificial intelligence to make the retrospective faster, more dynamic, and for time to be invested more productively. It needs to be a collaboration between the human component and artificial intelligence. - A mutual exchange. AI provides information that wouldn't be so obvious to the facilitator, given the many problems they face on a daily basis. - I see a pairing, a joint effort where the human factor leads, orders, limits and matures the use of the tool. - "Collaboratively, the human facilitator provides context, empathy, and critical judgment, while the AI tool offers detailed analysis, processing large volumes of data, and informed suggestions. - Complementary Skills: Each entity compensates for the other's limitations, resulting in more comprehensive and accurate decisions and solutions." - I see it being most useful in after the retrospective for analysis. Potentially however, prior to the retrospective an AI tool could analyze work done during the sprint period, meetings, etc. and provide a list of retro items to consider. So often teams are so busy that we forget things that have occurred that might be a good topic for retrospective. - I think I'd lean pretty hard on the human for laying out instructions and promoting conversation and lean on the AI for distilling information after the fact instead of talking to AI during a retro. - i think similar to most ai tools out there, by chat. also, maybe inserting files such as a screenshot of the retro or even an audio file - "By offloading administrative and data-intensive tasks to AI, the human Scrum Master can dedicate more time to critical activities that require human qualities, such as: - Coaching and mentoring the team. - Resolving conflicts and fostering positive team dynamics. - Promoting a strong Agile mindset. - Building relationships with stakeholders. - I believe there must be a good understanding of how to use the platform, and all the resources it can offer, to then evaluate what should be used or not. - As I mentioned earlier, it's important to evaluate the tool's suggestions and weigh up the team's opinions as well. - AI tool should be complementary to the human facilitator's skills and be able to perform the routine tasks so that the human facilitator can focus on higher level responsibilities - I could imagine a scenario where the retro was led by AI because that would take any human bias out of the retro process. Potentially the AI could generate several questions and then each person in the retro could pick one that everyone has to answer.

Question	Response
<p>What responsibilities do you believe should remain exclusively with the human facilitator?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain how the ceremony works, the confidentiality of shared information, choosing the best dynamic given the team's current situation and the problems observed. - As a moderator - Addressing teammates by name (AI recommendations should be agnostic of names); deciding how to solicit for responses i.e. the act of facilitating - Choose which AI suggestions make sense, don't let the AI take over the entire process - Ultimate responsibility. AI is just a tool. And like any tool it's only as good as the person wielding it. It's not intelligent or self aware. They're just extremely good pachinko machines. Humans should always have the final say. We should always check AI outputs against human experience. Using an LLM to gain insights and direction could be extremely useful to guide the conversation, but that human interaction is still the most important element. - Creating a safe environment and helping the team find effective ways to improve their performance remains the responsibility of the facilitator. - Dialogue with the team. While AI can assist the facilitator, it shouldn't replace them. - Decision-making on actions that come from retrospective or the use of AI in general. The tools will be powerful in insights and data search, analysis and recommendations, but every decision that the tool recommends must be human. - Strategic Decision Making, Empathy and Conflict Resolution, Goal Setting and Ethics, Contextual Interpretation - Actually running the meeting and eliciting comments. - answer above - having a good judgment call and discernment to choose if the response was actually appropriate and also making sure the team follows what's suggested as action items - The facilitator provides essential human qualities like empathy, adaptability, and emotional intelligence, which are crucial for effective communication and relationship building, particularly in complex or sensitive situations. - Final decision making - How I envision the process: AI, knowing the team's characteristics, can suggest a series of retro templates for the SM to choose from. The SM presents the retro contract and leads each phase of the meeting. In the final phase, the AI summarizes the positive and negative points and suggests how problems can be mitigated and positive points increased. These points raised by the AI can be evaluated by the team and the facilitator to determine what truly makes sense. In other words, the facilitator still manages most of the ceremony, simply assisted by a tool. However, using AI always requires an additional step of reviewing what was suggested. - Final decision making, building team dynamics and rapport - Final decisions; Ordering priorities - I think there will always be some things that AI suggests that we don't want to do, so having the option to redirect the conversation would be important. I think also having a human voice lead the retro helps.

Question	Response
<p>In what type of retrospective (e.g., newly formed teams, high-performance teams, post-failure analysis) do you believe AI would be most useful?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More useful in more mature teams. In newer teams, it can lead to greater insecurity and a greater chance of members not sharing the basic information needed to make the moment work. - post-failure analysis - norming new teams - All - New teams need to get to know each other and form a tight working relationship and expectations of each other and the processes and systems they expect to use. This needs to be organic in my opinion. High performing teams may find LLM based feedback useful if it's consistent and actionable. They're already high performing. How can AI help them get to that next level? I think it may be able to analyze the entire team workflow to make some recommendations. On projects that fail I'm not so sure it could be useful? This is often driven by a business decision or a team decision made along the way. In my experience it's often because leadership had high hopes and didn't give the team the autonomy or time to succeed. - Mature teams with high performance and failure analysis. Newly formed teams or those composed of members with little experience in agile methodologies could be more negatively impacted by the use of artificial intelligence in the retrospective process. - in newly formed teams and high-performance teams - I really want to apply it to teams that don't have a clear diagnosis of their problems, that have poor metrics or low NPS. I believe that AI can provide valuable recommendations for team recovery, removing the inevitable emotional human factor from a team that lives together on a daily basis. - In newly formed teams and after post-failure analysis, AI can help identify early patterns of behavior and processes that, if left unadjusted, could lead to future problems. - I think AI could have a role in any team that has a good, willing to participate, group. - post-failure analysis and newly formed teams I think identify metrics or data points where things can be improved. - any of them - AI based retros would be most useful for a high performing team - I believe it can be useful for all types of teams. For example, in new teams, it can help measure the pros and cons of decisions that need to be made. In post-failure analysis, it can help analyze what happened and how it can be corrected. In high-performance teams, it can help think about more complex technical changes. - I believe in all types. - AI in post failure analysis would be most beneficial since it can be 'fed' a lot of data and allow it to provide objective observations - high-performance teams and post-failure analysis - I think it could be helpful in all of these scenarios, especially with newly formed teams to create an open dialogue. I also think it would be very helpful in post failure analysis because it can ask more open questions than humans might feel comfortable asking.

Question	Response
<p>In your opinion, in which types of contexts would the use of AI in agile retrospectives be most beneficial? Do you think its impact would be greater in regular meetings or in specific moments, such as crises, organizational changes, or periods of rapid growth? Why?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In times of stability. Bringing AI into play during times of insecurity and uncertainty can only exacerbate these feelings among team members. - depends on the project and several factors such as team dynamics, project requirements, and even organizational structure - most beneficial in contexts that have very little drama - Depending on the use in all, I believe that in times of crisis it is the most complicated time, we need to turn off the autopilot and take charge of the process, following all possible precautions to not worsen the situation. - I like the idea of using it for post sprint analysis. Once the tools can reach into all of your systems and collate the data to make some good recommendations that'll be extremely valuable. Also given that set of sprint retrospectives, recommendations both LLM and Human, it would be interesting to see how those were implemented and which of the set was most effective for the team. Crisis moments seem very human driven to me. LLMs are only good if they're trained on the correct data. I can only see this working well if an LLM has been trained to recognize different crisis types and perhaps use that to predict the chance of crisis on a team given past and current performance. How would it handle someone leaving the team or interpersonal relationship issues? It can't. - I believe that, except for the initial periods of team formation, the use of artificial intelligence could be beneficial both in daily activities and in accelerating the resolution of specific problems and crises. - I believe the best scenario would be over the course of several sprints. - All cases seem powerful to me. I have doubts about using it for organizational changes. I still see a more human factor here than an AI factor. Given intangible contexts that do not come from data, it is difficult to diagnose with AI. For example: hierarchical cultures, inefficient and complex operations and structures, behavioral changes, and so on.... When you have a team with a crisis that has already been diagnosed, the specific data from that context can be better used. Good luck on that! =D - In contexts of structural or behavioral changes, in times of crisis, organizational changes, and periods of rapid growth, AI can improve regular meetings, bringing more added and significant value in situations that require rapid analysis and responses. - AI generated transcripts or the ability to analyze the web based too input for retro patterns would be very useful. This, in my opinion, helps to identify recurring areas of concern or recurring areas of strength that can be highlighted and actioned if needed. - I think there are different parts of AI that can apply to different situations and just like all tools, finding the right tool for the situation at hand will be most beneficial. So socializing all the tools and have awareness and understanding for what each tool excels at. - I think any of them - "The impact would be greater in regular meetings. The humans can dedicate more time to critical activities that require human qualities if AI can take over mundane tasks - I think it depends more on the team's maturity in knowing when to use the tool. If the team already has experience with the tool, it can be used in all situations; otherwise, it should only be used when there is an opportunity to learn from it. - I believe it would be interesting to always use it, even in the event of a crisis, to have a summary of data on how it got there, for example. - Regular meetings would be best for now since this seems more of a routine. Crises can benefit from AI tools with providing objective results, but org changes require a lot more emotional intelligence and should be facilitated by humans - I think only specific moments, so as not to limit the retrospective options that teams may want to conduct. I believe it should be an aid and not an AI-based retrospective. - I think it would be most helpful if used consistently so that there isn't the need to train with it when a stressful period occurs.

Triangulated Results

This appendix presents the triangulated results, combining insights from the qualitative interviews, the scientific literature (via snowballing), and the grey literature. The triangulation highlights convergences, complementarities, and divergences between sources, reinforcing transparency and methodological rigor.

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT1	Retrospectives are recognized as a pillar of continuous improvement and should be preserved as an essential space for collective learning.	Broad and positive experience	S2-B3 (Matthies 2019 – retros as continuous improvement); S3-F1-B1 (Hoda et al. 2018 – evolution of Agile)	Medium – <i>Value of Retrospectives</i>
RT2	The effectiveness of retrospectives depends on team culture and maturity; AI should adapt recommendations to the team’s stage.	Cultural/maturity variability	S3-F1-B3 (Masood et al. 2022 – real-world Scrum variations); S2-B3-B (Hoda et al. 2010 – self-organization)	McKinsey – <i>New Management Science</i>
RT3	There is a risk of formal yet ineffective retrospectives; AI can support structure and focus to avoid empty meetings.	Superficial/ineffective retros	S1-B2-F1 (Salimi-moghadam et al. 2025 – AI adoption barriers); S2-B3-F (Firdaus et al. 2019 – agile monitoring system)	Medium – <i>Agile Methodology in the Age of AI</i>
RT4	AI should reinforce the continuous-improvement nature of retrospectives, turning insights into trackable actions.	Retros as continuous improvement	S2-B3-B (Santana et al. 2015 – SPI in Agile); S3-F1-F3 (Babulak et al. 2025 – human-centered tools in Agile)	Atlassian – <i>AI Tools for Ticket Categorization</i>
RT5	Classic formats remain useful; AI should recommend the model best suited to the team’s goals and maturity.	Classic formats (Start–Stop–Continue, etc.)	S2-B3-B (Kuhrmann et al. 2015 – SPI in Agile); S1-B3-F6 (Rath et al. 2025 – SLR of Agile projects)	Medium – <i>AI-Powered Agility in the Software Industry</i>
RT6	Digital tools already structure retrospectives; AI can boost customization and integration with the backlog/Jira.	Use of templates and digital platforms	S3-F3-F3 (Kula et al. 2024 – automated sprint plans)	Atlassian – <i>MyAgileCopilot</i>
RT7	AI can suggest metaphors and creative variations, adapting them to engage the team.	Visual/playful dynamics	S3-F1-F4 (Nguyen-Duc & Khanna 2024 – ChatGPT adoption in Agile)	Medium – <i>How AI is Reshaping the Agile Sprint Cycle</i>
RT8	Retros must be contextualized; AI should assist the facilitator in choosing a format according to maturity, size, and remote/on-site context.	Adaptation to team context	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop agents, ICSE 2025)	Medium – <i>Agile Methodology in the Age of AI</i>

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT9	AI should ensure visibility of post-retro actions, track progress, and notify pending items, closing the continuous-improvement loop.	Emphasis on actions and follow-up	S2-B3-F (Guerrero-Calvache & Hernández 2024 – productivity metrics in Agile); S1-B2-B5 (Serrador & Pinto 2015 – success factors)	Atlassian – <i>AI Tools for Ticket Categorization</i> ; arXiv – <i>More Data-informed Retrospectives</i>
RT10	AI should act as a technical <i>co-pilot</i> (code skeletons, test cases, diagnostics) linked to stories , recording artifacts in the tracker and preserving traceability.	Software development support (prototyping, autocomplete, tests, debug)	S3-B1-F4 (GPT2SP – Transformer for SP); S3-B1-F2 (SP with XAI); S3-B1-F11 (SP vs. actual effort); S3-B1-F12 (Agile OSS dataset)	Medium – “Unleashing the Power of AI in Scrum”; Medium – “AI-Powered Agility”; Atlassian Community – “AI tools for ticket categorization”
RT11	AI should standardize summarization and documentation (meetings, ticket comments, stories), with metadata and sources for audit and reuse in later cycles.	Content generation and summarization (stories, meetings, brainstorm)	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile – human in the loop); S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop agents, ICSE); S3-F1-F4 (Survey on ChatGPT adoption in Agile)	arXiv – “More Data-informed Retrospectives”; Medium – “Summarizing team surveys for retrospectives”
RT12	AI should correlate sprint metrics with risk patterns and propose explainable (XAI) recommendations to focus the retro and planning.	Data and metrics analysis (velocity, lead time, burn-down)	S2-B1 (Predicting Delivery Capability, TSE); S3-F3 (Context-Aware Sprint Plan Generation, ASE 2024); S2-B1-F5 (Modeling Team Dynamics for delays); S2-B1-F1 (Sprint capacity prediction)	McKinsey – “A New Management Science for Tech Delivery”; Atlassian – “AI Tools for Ticket Categorization”
RT13	AI should assist POs/SMs (agendas, readiness checks, icebreakers, follow-ups) without replacing human judgment; operate in assistive mode with usage controls and opt-out .	Support for PO/SM activities (facilitation, engagement)	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S3-F1-B3 (Real-World Scrum – practice variations); S3-F1-F2 (Augmented Agile keynote)	Medium – “Why AI does not replace an SM”; Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot
RT14	AI should refine and prioritize the backlog with transparent criteria (value, risk, dependencies, cost of delay) and display explanations of weights/heuristics.	Task and backlog organization (create/estimate/prioritize)	S1-B3-F4 (XAI for requirements prioritization); S2-B2-F1/F4 (SLR effort estimation and ensembles); S3-F3 (Sprint Plan Generation)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; Medium – “AI in the backlog”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT15	AI should automate reports/dashboards (sprint status, trends, deviations) with links to evidence (tickets, PRs, incidents).	Report and dashboard creation	S3-F4-F2 (Adoption of generative chatbots by PMs); S3-F4-F1/F3 (AI in PM – studies/SLRs)	McKinsey – “Mgmt Science”; Corporate reports (Atlassian)
RT16	AI should adapt ceremonies to context (e.g., <i>planning</i> with predicted capacity limits; <i>retro</i> with data- and sentiment-oriented agendas).	Applications in agile ceremonies (retros, reviews, planning)	S3-F3 (Context-Aware Plan); S2-B1 (Delivery Capability); S3-F1 (Augmented Agile)	arXiv – “Data-informed Retrospectives”; Medium – “Reshaping the Sprint Cycle”
RT17	AI should automate operational work (summaries, action items, status) and persist actions with owners and due dates , feeding the improvement cycle.	Productivity accelerator / repetitive tasks (summaries, status, action items)	S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop agents); S3-F1 (Augmented Agile)	Medium – “Prompts for AI in Scrum”; Atlassian – automations
RT18	AI should recommend decisions with confidence levels/intervals and surface trade-offs , allowing team calibration.	Decision support (data-driven recommendations)	S2-B1-F3/F6 (replications/validation of estimation models); S3-B2-F5 (Bayesian for delays)	McKinsey – “Mgmt Science”; Atlassian – data-informed practices
RT19	AI should provide initial and interval estimates , adjusted by the team’s history and with explanations of factors (text, functional size, risks).	Better estimation and planning (effort/deadline prediction)	S3-B1-F4 (GPT2SP); S3-B1-F2 (XAI for SP); S2-B2-F1/F4 (SLRs on estimation/ensembles); S2-B1 (capacity)	Medium – AI cases for SP; Atlassian – Jira integrations
RT20	AI should generate/check test checklists linked to stories , suggesting coverage gaps and likely regressions.	Quality and testing support (cases, coverage)	S3-B1-F9 (NLP for functional size); S3-B1-F10 (DL for SP with improvements); DL in SE literature (S3-B2-F10)	Medium – “test generation with AI”
RT21	AI should suggest focused agendas from data + sentiment patterns , and consolidate feedback into actionable items .	Meeting/agenda organization and feedback collection	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S3-F1-F4 (adaptation with ChatGPT)	Medium – “team agendas and surveys”
RT22	AI should detect dependencies and emerging risks , propose mitigations (reordering, slicing, <i>spikes</i>) and signal impact on capacity .	Dependency and risk identification	S3-B2-F3 (Context-Aware Sprint Plan); S3-B2-F8 (User-story instability); S3-B2-F5 (Delay patterns + Bayes)	Atlassian – discussions on dependencies; Medium – “logjams and blockers”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT23	Adoption governance: AI as an assistant with explainability, audit trails, roles and policies , plus progressive onboarding for teams with no prior experience.	Human complement (does not replace) / No experience / No opinion	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile – human in the loop); S1-B2-B1 (AI adoption in PM – barriers); S1-B2-F1 (Opportunities and enablers)	Medium – “Why AI can’t replace a Scrum Master”; Corporate accounts
RT24	Implement progressive onboarding of AI in retros (light pilots, opt-in, clear roles/limits), prioritizing assistive mode and governance to reduce adoption barriers.	Did not use tools (adoption gap)	S1-B2-B1; S1-B2-F1 (adoption, barriers/enablers); S3-F1 (Augmented Agile)	Medium – “Why AI Can’t Replace a Scrum Master”; McKinsey – “Mgmt Science”
RT25	Instrument the retro with structured collection (tags, voting, ticket evidence) to enable basic analyses (freq., co-occurrence) and close the loop between meeting and backlog.	Generic use without analysis (just the dynamic)	S3-F1 (assistive role); S3-F4-F2/F6 (chatbot appropriation/SLRs)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; Medium – “Prompts for retros”
RT26	Move from superficial outputs (word clouds) to explainable thematic clustering (topics + examples), preserving traceability to cards/comments.	Partial support (word clouds/surveys)	S3-B2-F12 (topic modeling in SE); S3-F1-F4 (ChatGPT adoption)	arXiv – “Data-informed Retrospectives”
RT27	Use AI for sentiment, recurrence, and bottlenecks across sprints, highlighting trends and alerts that fuel agenda and follow-up.	Tool with AI and analytical support (sentiment/patterns)	S3-F2-B2 (Impediments via NLP); S2-B1 (Delivery Capability); S3-B2-F5 (delay patterns + Bayes)	Medium – “Reshaping the Sprint Cycle”
RT28	Standardize auditable summarization (sources, dates, links) of key problems/insights, reducing triage time during the retro.	Information summary and synthesis	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop agents)	arXiv – “Data-informed Retrospectives”; Medium – “Summaries for retros”
RT29	Group similar items with explainable labels, supporting assisted merge/split and showing exemplars that justify each cluster.	Clustering and topic grouping	S3-B2-F12 (topic modeling); S3-B1-F13 (clustering for SP)	Atlassian Community – “AI tools for categorization”
RT30	Prioritize topics by impact/recurrence/cost of delay and suggest SMART action items with explanations (XAI) and confidence level.	Action suggestions and prioritization	S1-B3-F4 (XAI for requirements prioritization); S3-F3 (Sprint Plan Generation); S2-B2-F4 (ensembles)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; Medium – “Prioritization prompts”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT31	Maintain a longitudinal history (“ <i>retro of retros</i> ”) to measure recurrence , action impact, and time to resolution .	Sentiment/pattern analysis (longitudinal)	S3-F2-B2; S3-B2-F6 (changes in SPs); S3-B2-F8 (story instability)	McKinsey – “Mgmt Science”
RT32	Run pre-analyses (sprint data) to build the agenda and post-analyses to measure action effects, with alerts when goals stall.	Pre- and post-retro support (full cycle)	S2-B1 (capacity prediction); S3-F3 (context-aware planning)	arXiv – “Data-informed Retrospectives”
RT33	Offer what-if simulations (reordering, slicing, WIP policies), estimating trade-offs (risk, lead time, capacity).	Scenario generation and recommendations	S3-B2-F5 (Bayes + delay patterns); S3-F3 (automated planning)	Medium – “What-if / simulations”
RT34	Address trust with explainability , scope controls , auditable logs , and opt-out per team/ceremony.	Skepticism/doubts (trust)	S3-F1 (human in the loop); S3-B1-F2 (XAI for SP); S1-B2-B1 (adoption barriers)	Medium – “Why AI ≠ SM”
RT35	Link clusters to root causes (dependencies, flow, quality) and suggest countermeasures (spikes, review policies, WIP limits).	Problem grouping/prioritization (root cause)	S2-B1-F5 (team dynamics→delays); S3-F4-F10 (predictive risk for continuity)	Atlassian – dependency practices
RT36	Generate sprint scorecards (capacity, throughput, rework, flow) to support decisions and verify action effectiveness.	Performance analysis and metrics (scorecards)	S3-F3-B3 (metrics in Agile/Lean); S2-B3-F (productivity metrics)	Corporate reports (Atlassian/McKinsey)
RT37	Use AI to flag unbalanced participation/sentiment patterns , suggest dynamics (1–2–4–All, internal NPS) and inclusive facilitation scripts .	Support for psychological safety / general insights	S3-F1 (human values in Agile); S3-F1-B4 (human values in SAFe)	Medium – facilitation/engagement cases
RT38	Adopt privacy by design (anonymization, <i>data minimization</i> , limited retention), environment segregation , and sharing controls , with audit trails accessible to PO/SM.	Security and privacy (LGPD/GDPR)	S1-B2-B1 (AI adoption in PM – barriers); S1-B2-F1 (SLR opportunities/enablers/barriers); S3-F4-B2 (PMBOK7 – measurement/risk domains)	McKinsey – <i>A New Management Science</i> ; Atlassian – integrations and best practices
RT39	Operate in assistive XAI mode : every recommendation must include justifications , sources , and confidence , preserving human approval before impacting backlog/process.	Skepticism about reliability (hallucinations/irrelevance)	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile – human in the loop); S3-B1-F2 (SP with XAI); S3-B1-F5/F6 (replications/generalization limits)	Medium – “Why AI can’t replace a Scrum Master”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT40	Incremental adoption roadmap (MVP per squad, value metrics, and adoption-specific retros), with leadership sponsorship and ethical checkpoints .	Organizational barriers (culture/rigid processes)	S1-B2-B3 (enablers/inhibitors); S3-F1-B3 (real Scrum variations); S2-B3-B (SPI in Agile)	Corporate accounts (Atlassian); Medium – adoption cases
RT41	Business case with outcome metrics (retro prep time, % actions completed, recurrence reduction), choosing cost models per use/seat and starting with high-impact cases .	Cost and licensing	S1-B2-B2 (maturity/expectations of AI in PM); S3-F4-F6/F9 (impacts/PM2030 agenda)	McKinsey – ROI of analytics/AI; Atlassian – automations
RT42	Light, time-box-friendly UX: templates for agenda/clustering/prioritization and guided assistants in Jira/board, with quick training and in-context help .	Learning curve and usability	S3-F1-F4 (adoption of ChatGPT in Agile); S3-F1-F1 (HITL agents)	Medium – “prompts and templates”; Atlassian – <i>playbooks</i>
RT43	Human-in-the-loop policy: AI does not run the retro; it prepares inputs (summaries, clusters, options), while people decide and moderate.	Fear of process dehumanization	S3-F1 (Human-Centered AI); S3-F1-B4 (human values in SAFe)	Medium – “Why AI ≠ SM”
RT44	Native integrations (Jira/Confluence/boards), connectors to sprint data, and API/credential governance , ensuring traceability (ticket→analysis→action).	Technical requirements and integration	S3-F3 (Context-Aware Sprint Plan Generation); S2-B1 (Capacity prediction)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; Atlassian Community – <i>AI categorization</i>
RT45	Prioritize official plugins and workflows already in use, avoiding context switching and reducing adoption friction.	Integration with existing tools (facilitator)	S3-F3; S3-F2-B6 (agents/story quality)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; <i>AI tools for ticket categorization</i>
RT46	Quick proofs of value (A/B per squad, 2–3 sprints) with defined KPIs and retro review to decide expand/adjust .	Demonstration of practical value (facilitator)	S1-B2-B5 (Agile and project success); S2-B3-F (productivity metrics)	McKinsey – impact cases
RT47	Responses in seconds , few clicks , ready-made prompts , and manual fallback (when confidence is low).	Agility/usability (facilitator)	S3-F1-F1 (HITL agents); S3-F1 (Augmented Agile)	Medium – “no bureaucracy/time”
RT48	Automate the operational side of the retro (summaries, action drafts, follow-up), freeing team time for root-cause discussion .	Delegation of undesirable tasks (facilitator)	S3-F1; S3-F3 (automated planning)	Medium – “delegating responsibilities”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT49	Scale by capabilities: start with summary+clustering , then prioritization , then what-if ; define scope and limits per ceremony.	Progressive adoption and clear scope (facilitator)	S1-B2-B1; S1-B2-F1 (enablers/barriers)	Atlassian/McKinsey – rollout best practices
RT50	Safety cards (DPIA/LIA), role-based access controls , logs , and standard explainability in retro reports.	Trust and security (facilitator)	S3-B1-F2 (XAI); S3-F1 (human in the loop)	Organizational privacy/security policies
RT51	Executive sponsorship with clear goals (OKRs), budget , and communication about AI’s assistive role.	Organizational support (facilitator)	S1-B2-B3 (adoption enablers)	Corporate leadership accounts
RT52	Light and continuous training (micro-lessons + exemplar prompts), office hours , and AI champions in each squad.	Training and support (facilitator)	S3-F1-F4 (adoption); S3-F1-F1 (HITL agents)	Playbooks (Atlassian)
RT53	Adopt role-based access (team, PO/SM), time-windowed visibility, and explicit sharing scope for all AI-generated retro content.	Team access and control (scope/visibility)	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile – human in the loop); S1-B2-B1 (adoption: barriers/enablers)	Atlassian – integrations/controls; McKinsey – data-driven management principles
RT54	Every AI recommendation must include explanations , sources , linked evidence (tickets, metrics), and confidence/intervals .	Clarity and justification of recommendations (explainability)	S3-B1-F2 (XAI for SP estimation); S1-B3-F4 (XAI for prioritization)	Atlassian accounts (ticket traceability); Medium articles (explain recommendations)
RT55	Establish minimum quality criteria (accuracy, usefulness, feasibility) and team feedback loops to calibrate models and discard weak suggestions.	Recommendation quality and realism (usefulness)	S3-B1-F5/F6 (replications/robustness in estimation); S2-B1 (capacity prediction)	McKinsey – “proofs of value”; Atlassian – validation practices
RT56	Publish “ transparency cards ” (what data goes in, where it stays, for how long, who accesses, how the model was trained) and conduct DPIA/LIA .	Transparency in use/training (data and model)	S1-B2-F1 (opportunities/enablers/barriers – compliance); S3-F4-B2 (PMBOK7 – measurement/risk domains)	Organizational policies (privacy); McKinsey (governance)
RT57	Define a usage policy per ceremony (what AI does/does not do), operating limits , approval flow , and auditable logs .	Well-defined usage rules (policies)	S1-B2-B3 (inhibitors/enablers); S2-B3-B (SPI and governance)	Atlassian – usage playbooks; Medium – best practices

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT58	Offer multiple alternatives with comparative rationale (pros/cons, trade-offs) to preserve the team's autonomy of choice .	Varied options and alternative explanations (plurality)	S3-F3 (Context-Aware Plan Generation); S2-B2-F4 (ensembles)	Prompt playbooks (Medium)
RT59	When explained and traceable , AI can increase confidence in the process by standardizing prioritization criteria and reducing bias.	Potential to increase trust (objectivity)	S2-B1 (predictive models); S3-B2-F5 (Bayes for risk)	McKinsey – data-driven decisions
RT60	Implement privacy by design : anonymization, data minimization , short retention, processing scopes , and audit trails visible to PO/SM.	Privacy/confidentiality risk	S1-B2-B1; S1-B2-F1 (compliance/adoption)	Atlassian – controls/integration; internal policies
RT61	Run controlled pilots (2–3 sprints), clear objectives/KPIs and kill criteria when there is no gain; document learning in the retro.	Risk of distrust due to ineffectiveness	S3-B1-F5/F6 (generalization/replication limits); S3-F1 (HITL)	Corporate failure cases (grey)
RT62	Create a light governance committee (PO/SM/Security) to review usage, value metrics, and incidents , with periodic reporting .	Need for governance and transparency	S1-B2-B3 (enablers/inhibitors); S3-F4-F6 (broad reviews AI+PM)	McKinsey – analytics governance
RT63	Gradual introduction : start with summaries and clustering , then XAI prioritization , and finally what-if ; always with team opt-in .	Progressive adoption as mitigator	S1-B2-B1; S1-B2-F1 (incremental adoption)	Atlassian – rollout by plugin/team
RT64	The SM/coach mediates AI outputs (contextualizes, filters, arbitrates) and safeguards psychological safety and equity of voice .	Facilitator role (contextual mediation)	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S3-F1-B3 (real-world Scrum variations)	Medium – facilitation/engagement
RT65	Immutable logs of inputs/outputs, sign-offs on approved recommendations, and anomaly detection in inputs (spam, bias).	Concern about manipulation or misuse	S3-F4-F10 (predictive risk/continuity); S2-B3-B (practice evidence)	Atlassian – logs and permissions
RT66	Check-in rituals (trust check, retro NPS, “safe challenge” policy) to continuously discuss AI's role.	Open communication as mitigator	S3-F1-B4 (human values); S3-F1 (HITL)	Internal codes of conduct; best practices (grey)
RT67	Provide minimal onboarding (guided tour, examples, operating limits) before first use to set realistic expectations.	No expectations / undefined	S1-B2-B2 (maturity/expectations); S3-F4-F6 (adoption panoramas)	—

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT68	The retro should operate in assistive mode : AI structures data and options; the facilitator orchestrates , mediates, and decides with the team.	Complementary human-AI collaboration	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile: human in the loop); S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop software agents)	McKinsey – <i>A New Management Science</i> ; Medium – “Why AI Can’t Replace a Scrum Master”
RT69	Forbid delegating facilitation to AI: it prepares inputs and recommendations; conduct remains exclusively human .	AI as support tool, not facilitator	S3-F1; S3-F1-B4 (human values in SAFe)	Medium – “Why AI ≠ SM”
RT70	Automate summaries, metric extraction, action tracking, and backlog sync to free time for discussion.	Automation of administrative tasks (offload)	S3-F3 (Context-Aware Sprint Plan Generation); S2-B1 (Capacity prediction)	Atlassian – MyAgileCopilot; Atlassian Community – “AI tools for ticket categorization”
RT71	Perform pre-analyses (trends, recurrence, bottlenecks) and propose an initial agenda and root-cause hypotheses.	Retro preparation support (pre-analysis)	S3-B2-F5 (patterns/risk Bayes); S3-B2-F6 (SP changes); S3-F3 (planning)	arXiv – “Data-informed Retrospective Activities”
RT72	Prioritize native integrations (Jira, Git, Slack) with traceability ticket→insight→action, reducing context switching.	Interaction via integrated systems (Jira/Git/Slack)	S3-F3; S2-B1 (operational data)	Atlassian – integrations (Jira/Confluence)
RT73	Offer task-oriented chat (upload screenshots/logs) with question templates and quick replies compatible with the time-box.	Interaction via chat or files	S3-F1-F4 (LLM adoption in Agile)	Medium – prompts/templates; Atlassian – practices
RT74	Use AI to surface biases (unequal participation, recency effect) and present alternatives with pros/cons , keeping decisions human.	Use to mitigate human bias	S3-B1-F2 (XAI for SP – interpretability); S3-F1 (human-centered)	McKinsey – data-driven decisions
RT75	Make human review mandatory before any AI-suggested change to process/backlog.	Final decision and critical judgment (SM/coach)	S3-F1 (HITL); S3-B1-F5/F6 (model limits/replications)	Medium – facilitation guides
RT76	The facilitator ensures psychological safety : AI only flags patterns (e.g., recurring silence) without exposing individuals.	Safe environment and active listening	S3-F1-B4 (human values in SAFe); S3-F1 (Augmented Agile)	Medium – psychological safety practices
RT77	The facilitator selects the dynamic and uses AI to adjust pace/agendas , never to control people’s speaking/time.	Ceremony conduction and mediation (engagement)	S3-F1 (human-centered)	Atlassian – ceremony playbooks

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT78	Conflicts and sensitive topics are mediated by humans ; AI may only suggest scripts and neutral language .	Empathy, EI, and sensitivity (conflicts)	S3-F1; S3-F1-B3 (real-world Scrum variations)	—
RT79	AI outputs must be contextualized to the team’s history (capacity, maturity, policies), avoiding “one-size-fits-all.”	Contextual interpretation (history/culture)	S2-B1 (team-context capacity); S3-F3 (context-aware)	—
RT80	Require explanations and evidence for each recommendation (XAI) and allow discard/edit with recorded rationale .	Assessing the relevance of AI suggestions	S3-B1-F2 (XAI); S3-B1-F5/F6 (generalization limits)	—
RT81	AI is useful in post-mortems : extracts root causes from large volumes of logs/incidents, reducing bias and accelerating learning.	Post-failure (post-mortem)	S3-B2-F5 (risk/pattern analysis); S3-F1 (HITL for diagnostics)	Atlassian – “Incident retrospective playbooks”; Medium – “AI for post-mortems”
RT82	In new teams, AI can suggest dynamics , map initial communication patterns , and facilitate alignment .	Newly formed teams	S3-F1-B3 (Scrum variations at the start); S3-F3 (initial team support)	Medium – “AI onboarding retrospectives”
RT83	In already efficient teams, AI acts as an optimizer , identifying subtle bottlenecks and promoting incremental continuous improvement.	High-performance teams	S3-F1-F1 (Human-in-the-loop agents in mature teams)	McKinsey – “Next-level agile with AI”
RT84	General applicability, as long as maturity and context are respected; AI can be adapted to any retro format.	All types/retrospectives	S3-F1 (Augmented Agile); S2-B1 (prediction applicable to any team)	Atlassian – “AI use cases across ceremonies”
RT85	Mature teams tend to extract more value from AI data due to analysis discipline and established reflective culture.	Mature and experienced teams	S3-B2-F6 (SP change in stable teams)	—
RT86	AI can offer an objective diagnosis to low-clarity teams, but requires human mediation to avoid reinforcing insecurities.	Low-performance teams/poor metrics	S3-B1 (agile performance evaluation via metrics)	—
RT87	Recurring use empowers AI to detect longitudinal patterns and assess action evolution across multiple sprints.	Regular meetings (continuous use)	S2-B1 (longitudinal team data); S3-B2 (tracking across sprints)	Atlassian – “AI memory across retrospectives”
RT88	AI is useful in crises or change , as it accelerates diagnosis and produces quick options—always under sensitive human mediation .	Critical moments (crises, change, growth)	S3-F1 (HITL in organizational change)	Medium – “AI in organizational change retros”

ID	Triangulated Finding	Category (Open Coding)	Scientific Evidence (IDs)	Gray Literature (Source)
RT89	Maturity determines whether AI helps or hinders; experienced teams extract value, novices require strong facilitator support .	Depends on team maturity	S3-F1-B4 (human values modulating AI impact)	—
RT90	In crises, AI should play a secondary role ; humans lead, prioritizing empathy and psychological safety .	Crisis as a non-ideal scenario	S3-F1 (risk of dehumanization)	Atlassian – “Psychological safety first”
RT91	The benefit depends on the tool and application context ; there is no “universal AI” for retrospectives.	Depends on use/tool	S3-F1-F4 (selective LLM adoption in Agile)	Medium – “Choose the right AI tool for your retro”
RT92	AI can diversify dynamics and suggest proper spacing of retros, avoiding fatigue and repetitive formats.	Repetitive formats and frequency	S3-F1-F2 (Hoda 2024 – Augmented Agile keynote); S3-F3-B3 (Kupainen et al. 2015 – metrics in Agile/Lean)	Medium – <i>Unleashing the Power of AI in Scrum</i>
RT93	Operate AI only in assistive mode ; final decisions and prioritization are human-in-the-loop , with possible override and opt-out per team.	Complement to human reflection (not a replacement)	S3-F1 (Human-Centered AI); S3-F1-B4 (human values in SAFe)	Medium – “Why AI can’t replace a Scrum Master”